

**Downscaling climate impacts and decarbonisation pathways
In EU Islands, and enhancing socioeconomic and non-market
evaluation of Climate Change for Europe, for 2050 and beyond**

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Work Package 4: Modelling Climate impacts in 11 EU islands' case studies for 2030- 2100

Deliverable 4.4a: Report on solar and wind energy for different scenarios and different time horizons

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1. Introduction

Together with the energy section of D4.3, this report is related to Objective 1 of SOCLIMPACT: “Develop a thorough understanding on how Climate Change will impact the EU islands located in different regions of the world, considering their specific vulnerability, thus improving the existing climate impact models.” This is done by analysing the results, presented with maps in D4.3, regarding the following energy indicators: (i) wind energy productivity, (ii) photovoltaic productivity, (iii) wind productivity droughts, (iv) photovoltaic productivity droughts and (v) combined photovoltaic and wind productivity droughts. Energy droughts is a term used to refer to low-productivity periods (Raynaud et al., 2018) and can provide information that is also relevant for mitigation purposes, as in future decarbonisation scenarios the frequency and duration of such droughts will determine the needed amount of energy storage and backup sources. Therefore, the indicators considered in the present report are related also to Objective 4: “Facilitate climate-related policy decision making for Blue Growth, by ranking and mapping the more appropriate and viable mitigation, adaptation and risk management strategies, ...” and Objective 5: “..., and formulate science-based recommendations to incentivise the EU islands medium to long-term low-carbon transition, ...”. All the results presented here have been calculated specifically for SOCLIMPACT.

Solar PV and wind energy have been selected as they are presently, and likely also in the future, the backbone of the deployment of renewable energies, due to their technological maturity and low cost. As a specifically marine energy source we take into account offshore wind energy, in addition to onshore wind energy. To this end, we consider domains around the islands or archipelagos with boundaries at a distance of about 1 degree from the extremes of the islands in all four directions, as offshore wind parks are frequently located at a distance of about 100 km or less from the coast.

We also calculate PV productivity over the same domain, including the sea. On the one hand, this is done for consistency reasons as we consider a combined PV-wind energy indicator. On the other hand, there is growing interest in offshore solar energy. Offshore PV has advantages for islands or countries with limited space for the installation of solar panels, apart from the increased performance due to the cooling effect of the water on PV cells. The installation of floating PV panels has been already tested over sea waters next to Malta (Grech et al., 2016), and one offshore PV farm is already operating near the coast of the Netherlands (Buitendijk, 2019), an area characterised by high waves.

The combination of different types of offshore renewable energy sources (including wind and solar) in the same platform is also attracting interest, as the different sources can exhibit complementarity in time and the combined output can thus be more stable and reliable, and they can also share part of the installations, like the connection to land, reducing their cost (MarineEnergy, 2019a). The European Union is trying to promote such combinations, through projects like MUSICA (Multiple Use of Space for Island Clean Autonomy) which will design and test a floating offshore platform integrating wind, PV and wave energy for use on islands (MarineEnergy, 2019b), and plans to develop roadmaps for its deployment in three case study islands, among them Malta and the Canaries (O'Connor, 2019). Therefore, the potential future

relevance of offshore PV makes it interesting to calculate also PV indicators over sea, particularly given the importance of marine energy in SOCLIMPACT.

In the case of solar and wind renewable energies, the impact of climate change may be also positive for some areas, if their productivity and/or their reliability are projected to increase in the future. We highlight this possibility in the tables showing our results, differentiating positive and negative impacts. The uncertainty of future projections is taken into account through the spread (maximum and minimum) of the different simulations in the multi-model ensembles used, and also through the consistency (or lack of it) in the sign of the projected changes among the different simulations.

We analyse several dimensions of these indicators. The spatial variability is shown in the figures of deliverable 4.3, while the land-sea contrast is presented here through spatially-averaged values in the tables. The characteristics of daily variability of productivity is considered through the energy drought frequency and duration, which allow us to discuss the reliability of these energy technologies. Two thresholds are considered following Raynaud et al. (2019): one for moderate droughts (50% of the average daily productivity) and one for severe droughts (20% of the average daily productivity). Finally, the effect on energy droughts of a 50/50 combination of PV and wind energy is also considered. Such a combination can provide a large improvement in the stability of energy output if the wind and solar resources are complementary. While a general analysis is performed for all islands considered in SOCLIMPACT, based on the obtained results we select three study cases for a more in-depth analysis including the seasonal variations of the indicators.

2. Methods and data

2.1 Wind energy productivity

This indicator will show potential changes in wind energy productivity (W_{prod}). Here, productivity (kWh/kW) is defined as the energy produced in a period of time divided by the power installed, which is considered as unitary. The methodology followed is the same used in the previous deliverable 4.3.

We first derive the wind speed at the surface (10 m, W_{10}) from 6-hourly U_{10} and V_{10} wind components of the simulations considered. Then, we calculate the wind speed W_H at the turbine hub height ($H = 100$ m for wind energy over land; $H = 150$ m over the sea). From Tobin et al. (2015):

$$W_H = W_{10} \cdot \left(\frac{H}{10}\right)^\alpha$$

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{7}$$

After calculating W_H at the turbine hub height, we calculate wind potential (W_{pot}) as in Jerez et al. (2015). However, in order to do that, W_H must be regarded as the average of the wind speed at 6-hours intervals (W_{av}):

$$W_{\text{av}} \left(\frac{t_{2i+1}}{2}\right) = \frac{[W_H(t_i) + W_H(t_{i+1})]}{2}$$

$$W_{\text{pot}} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } V < V_I \\ \frac{V^3 - V_I^3}{V_R^3 - V_I^3} & \text{if } V_I \leq V < V_R \\ 1 & \text{if } V_R \leq V < V_O \\ 0 & \text{if } V \geq V_O \end{cases}$$

where $V_I = 3$ m/s (cut-in wind velocity); $V_R = 12$ m/s (rated velocity); $V_O = 25$ m/s (cut-out velocity) and $V = W_{\text{av}}$.

Finally, wind productivity (W_{prod}) is calculated from the wind potential produced by the 6-hr averaged wind multiplied by the number of hours (6 hours).

2.2 Photovoltaic productivity

This indicator will show future changes in photovoltaic (PV) productivity. Productivity (kWh/kW) is defined as the energy produced in a period of time divided by the power capacity installed.

In order to obtain photovoltaic productivity, daily surface solar radiation (SSR) and ambient temperature from the climate simulations are used as input variables for a parametric PV model.

The PV modelling process can be summarised in two steps: first, incident solar radiation that reaches solar cells inside the panels is obtained through the decomposition of global solar irradiation and the transposition to the plane-of-array. After that, the electrical performance of the photovoltaic system is modelled in order to obtain daily PV productivity (PV_{prod}). To obtain annual or monthly statistics, the respective sum of daily productivity is computed in each case. A detailed description of the methodology was presented in Deliverable 4.3 (the methodology is the same followed in the Gutiérrez et al., 2017).

2.3 Renewable energy productivity droughts

In the frame of the SOCLIMPACT H2020 project, photovoltaic and wind energy productivity droughts are calculated as an indicator of productivity steadiness in the analysed European islands. Renewable energy droughts can be regarded as low-productivity periods during which the daily productivity takes values below a low-productivity threshold. To systematically identify energy droughts, a Deficiency Index (DI) is computed following Raynaud et al. (2018). This is defined as follows:

$$DI(i,j) = 1 \text{ if } P(i,j) \leq P_0(i,j)$$
$$DI(i,j) = 0 \text{ if } P(i,j) > P_0(i,j)$$

Where P is the daily productivity (kWh/kW) computed as explained in Sections 2.1 and 2.2 and P_0 the corresponding low-productivity threshold. Productivity thresholds are calculated as a percentage of the mean daily productivity estimated for the control time period, which goes from 1986 to 2005 in all cases with the exception of Azores, where it ranges from 1981 to 2000 due to the different set of climate simulations used. Thresholds to determine energy productivity droughts in the scenarios are also computed taking the mean daily productivity of the studied region in the control period. Two different thresholds are calculated to determine moderate and severe energy productivity droughts, respectively. Additionally, combined photovoltaic and wind productivity droughts are also calculated. More details about the methodology followed to compute energy productivity droughts can be found in the Methodology Section of Deliverable 4.3 dealing with energy indicators.

2.4 Climate simulations

Results here presented are calculated for each group of islands taking into consideration the following simulations:

Ensemble:	EURO-CORDEX				MENA-CORDEX			ESCENA			
RCM:	SMHI				SMHI			PROMES			
GCM:	MPI	IPSL	CNRM	MOHC	CNRM	GFDL	ICHEC	ARPEGE	ECHAM	HDQ03	HDQ16
AZO (3.1.3)								X	X	X	X
BALEI (3.2.3)	X	X	X	X							
BALTI (3.3.3)	X	X	X	X							
CAI (3.4.3)					X	X	X				
COR (3.5.3)	X	X	X	X							
CRE (3.6.3)	X	X	X	X							
CYP (3.7.3)	X	X	X	X							
MAD (3.8.3)					X	X	X				
ML (3.9.3)	X	X	X	X							
SAR (3.10.3)	X	X	X	X							
SIC (3.11.3)	X	X	X	X							

Table 2.1. Simulations considered for each island or archipelago (the number in brackets refers to the corresponding subsection in D4.3). RCM indicates the Regional Climate Model and GCM indicates the Global Climate Model: SMHI=SMHI-RCA4; PROMES=UCLM-PROMES MPI=MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR; IPSL=IPSL-IPSL-CM5A-MR; CNRM=CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5; MOHC=MOHC-HadGEM2-ES; GFDL=NOAA-GFDL-GFDL-ESM2M; ICHEC=ICHEC-EC-EARTH.

In this report we analyse different time periods. The control period (CTRL) extends from 1986 to 2005 for the EURO-CORDEX and MENA-CORDEX groups of simulations, and from 1981 to 2000 for the ESCENA simulations. With respect to the future scenarios here analysed, there are two different periods: one that goes from 2046 to 2065 and the other that corresponds to the end of the 21st century, from 2081 to 2100, both for EURO-CORDEX and MENA-CORDEX simulations. In the case of ESCENA simulations, the scenario period goes from 2031 to 2050.

The scenarios used depend on the experiment: the ESCENA ensemble of simulations uses the SRES A1B and B1 emission scenarios, whereas for the EURO-CORDEX and MENA-CORDEX the ‘representative concentration pathways’, RCPs, 2.6 and 8.5 are considered here. Note that for RCP2.6 scenario only simulations driven by MPI and MOHC GCMs are available in EURO-CORDEX, and ICHEC in MENA-CORDEX. For B1 scenario, only simulations driven by ARPEGE and ECHAM GCMs are available in ESCENA.

3. Results

In Section 3.1 we show and comment the most relevant results obtained for the energy indicators in the analysed islands. Results presented here include a set of tables which provide an overview of the ensemble mean and uncertainty values (maximum and minimum among the ensemble simulations) of the wind and photovoltaic productivity, as well as the energy productivity drought indicators. In Section 3.2 we show time series that are used to gain insight into the interannual and seasonal variability of the productivity indicators for three case studies, for which also a combined analysis of energy drought frequency and consecutive drought days is performed.

3.1 General analysis

In this section we present a series of tables which summarise the ensemble mean values of the three indicators considered: (i) wind energy productivity, (ii) PV productivity and (iii) energy productivity droughts. For clarity, two tables are given for each island: one for renewable energy productivity and another one for energy productivity droughts. Ensemble mean values of productivity are averaged separately over land and over sea, respectively. Ensemble mean values of productivity droughts (wind, PV and combined wind and PV) are exclusively calculated over land. For Azores, all indicators are calculated over the whole domain, which includes mainly sea points, due to the relatively coarse spatial resolution of the models used. Tables for the corresponding islands are presented in alphabetical order. To facilitate the interpretation of the results, the cells in which the scenarios show a decrease (increase) of the productivity or an increase (decrease) of the frequency of energy productivity droughts are shaded in orange (blue). The uncertainty in the sign of the changes is highlighted through the colour tone: a dark tone indicates coincidence in the sign among all ensemble members, while a light tone indicates that the sign is uncertain. The most relevant results obtained for each island are commented after the corresponding table. To make the description of these islands more complete, we will also refer to the corresponding figures presented regarding energy indicators in the atlas of Deliverable 4.3.

3.1.1 Azores

Azores		Wind Energy Prod		PV Prod	
		Land	Sea	Land	Sea
<i>CTRL</i>	<i>1981-2000</i>	x	4864 (4380 , 5337)	x	764 (705 , 835)
<i>B1</i>	<i>2031-2050</i>	x	-20 (-141 , 101)	x	7 (6 , 11)
<i>A1B</i>	<i>2031-2050</i>	x	62 (-181 , 193)	x	9 (9 , 10)

Table 1.1. Ensemble mean values of annual wind and solar productivity indicators (kWh/kW) in the control period (1981-2000) and ensemble mean changes in the future period (2031-2050) for the B1 and A1B scenarios. Ensemble minimum and maximum values are shown in brackets. In the simulations corresponding to the Azores region, land areas are too small and averages are computed over the whole domain, which is mainly sea. Blue (orange) colours indicate the positive (negative) changes in the scenarios relative to the control period. Dark blue and orange colours, respectively, are applied to those cells in which ensemble minimum and maximum values have the same sign. Light blue and orange colours indicate the opposite.

Azores		Wind		PV		Combined PV and Wind	
		Moderate	Severe	Moderate	Severe	Moderate	Severe
<i>CTRL</i>	<i>1981-2000</i>	29.6 (24.1 , 36.3)	15.2 (11.2 , 20.2)	24.3 (22.6 , 26.2)	6.4 (4.6 , 7.6)	25.1 (20.4 , 31.3)	4.4 (3.7 , 5.2)
<i>B1</i>	<i>2031-2050</i>	0.68 (-0.49 , 1.84)	0.74 (-0.22 , 1.70)	0.09 (-0.08 , 0.27)	0.18 (0.02 , 0.34)	0.55 (-0.63 , 1.72)	0.52 (0.06 , 0.98)
<i>A1B</i>	<i>2031-2050</i>	-0.50 (-2.41 , 1.74)	-0.29 (-1.87 , 1.39)	0.12 (-0.54 , 0.76)	-0.10 (-0.43 , 0.34)	-0.47 (-2.30 , 1.57)	0.13 (-0.42 , 0.75)

Table 1.2. Ensemble mean frequency of moderate and severe productivity drought days (%) in the control time period, as well as the ensemble mean changes in the frequency of drought days (%) in the different time periods considered for the A1B and B1 scenarios. Ensemble minimum and maximum values are given in brackets. Because land areas are too small, averages are computed over the whole domain, which is mainly sea. Blue (orange) colours indicate a drought decrease (increase) in the scenarios, relative to the control. The scenario changes are percentages with respect to the total number of days in the respective period, not with respect to the control value. Dark blue and orange colours, respectively, are applied to those cells in which ensemble minimum and maximum values have the same sign. Light blue and orange colours indicate the opposite.

Before we start with the description of the main findings for Azores, we would like to highlight that results for this region should be taken with caution since the Azores islands are near the model boundaries in ESCENA simulations, which can lead to important biases in the simulated variables, particularly solar radiation.

Wind energy productivity:

From Figure 3.1.3_E2_A (deliverable 4.3), it can be observed that the ensemble-mean projects an increase of W_{prod} for A1B emissions scenario for the period 2031-2050. This increase is highest for the islands located more to the southeast, while no changes or slight decreases to the northwest of the area are expected. In B1 scenario, a similar pattern of changes as in A1B is seen, but decreases are more extended than increases, so that the spatially averaged changes (Table 1.1) show a slight decrease in this case. The spatially averaged changes are rather small (ensemble mean changes are around 1%, which is partly due to a high model spread, as different models show changes of opposite sign and similar magnitude).

Photovoltaic energy productivity:

Annual photovoltaic productivity over the Azores Islands can be observed in Figure 3.1.3_E1_A (deliverable 4.3), with mean values between 650 to 750 kWh/kW. These values are below the ones expected with simulated and observed solar radiation found in the literature (Magarreiro, 2016). However, this negative bias is likely due to the fact that the region is very close to the model boundaries. For changes in both scenarios, A1B and B1 for the future period 2031-2050, a slight increase can be observed in both cases, with higher values in the eastern islands in the B1 scenario. The spatially averaged changes (Table 1.1) are small (around 1% with respect to the control period) for both scenarios, and the uncertainty is low in this case with a coincidence in sign among the different models.

Energy productivity droughts:

Moderate and severe wind droughts tend to experience a subtle increase in frequency, especially to the northwest of the domain, in the B1 scenario (see Figure 3.1.3_E3.1_A and Table 1.2). In the A1B scenario, the frequency of wind droughts tends to decrease, particularly to the southeast of the studied domain. Results obtained for the different scenarios are in line with wind productivity changes presented in Figure 3.1.3_E2_A. Regarding the frequency of moderate PV droughts, this increases (decreases) to the west (east) of the domain in both B1 and A1B scenarios (Figure 3.1.3_E4.1_A). Severe PV droughts, in contrast, experience a little increase in the B1 scenario and a subtle decrease in the A1B case. In most of the cases, there is uncertainty in the sign of change (Table 1.2).

3.1.2 Balearic Islands

<i>Balearic Islands</i>		<i>Wind Energy Prod</i>		<i>PV Prod</i>	
		<i>Land</i>	<i>Sea</i>	<i>Land</i>	<i>Sea</i>
<i>CTRL</i>	<i>1986-2005</i>	1769 (1628 , 1917)	3944 (3701 , 4196)	1559 (1502 , 1638)	1529 (1481 , 1581)
<i>RCP2.6</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	-74 (-115 , -32)	-79 (-99 , -60)	-2 (-5 , 0)	-13 (-16 , -11)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	-64 (-93 , -34)	-41 (-46 , -35)	-5 (-18 , 7)	-12 (-21 , -3)
<i>RCP8.5</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	-115 (-146 , -89)	-143 (-173 , -82)	-22 (-39 , -12)	-42 (-56 , -22)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	-223 (-302 , -176)	-322 (-423 , -249)	-36 (-56 , -18)	-78 (-102 , -52)

Table 2.1. Ensemble mean values of annual wind and solar productivity indicators (kWh/kW) in the control period (1986-2005) and ensemble mean changes in future periods (2046-2065, 2081-2100) for the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Ensemble minimum and maximum values are shown in brackets. Spatial averages are computed for land and sea separately. Blue (orange) colours indicate the positive (negative) changes in the scenarios relative to the control period. Dark blue and orange colours, respectively, are applied to those cells in which ensemble minimum and maximum values have the same sign. Light blue and orange colours indicate the opposite.

<i>Balearic Islands</i>		<i>Wind</i>		<i>PV</i>		<i>Combined PV and Wind</i>	
		<i>Moderate</i>	<i>Severe</i>	<i>Moderate</i>	<i>Severe</i>	<i>Moderate</i>	<i>Severe</i>
<i>CTRL</i>	<i>1986-2005</i>	52.5 (50.7 , 54.4)	31.6 (29.8 , 34.1)	7.1 (4.3 , 8.5)	1.2 (0.5 , 1.6)	12.6 (10.3 , 14.1)	0.6 (0.4 , 0.8)
<i>RCP2.6</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	1.29 (0.92 , 1.67)	0.67 (0.64 , 0.69)	-0.53 (-0.82 , -0.24)	-0.17 (-0.31 , -0.04)	-0.04 (-0.09 , 0.01)	-0.05 (-0.07 , -0.03)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	1.21 (0.88 , 1.53)	0.91 (0.72 , 1.10)	-0.44 (-0.92 , 0.03)	-0.23 (-0.42 , -0.04)	0.28 (-0.75 , 1.30)	0.05 (-0.16 , 0.26)
<i>RCP8.5</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	2.10 (1.48 , 2.87)	1.43 (0.84 , 2.24)	0.10 (-0.54 , 0.77)	0.05 (-0.17 , 0.29)	0.98 (0.40 , 2.53)	0.22 (0.06 , 0.58)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	4.67 (3.60 , 6.54)	3.57 (2.81 , 4.92)	-0.17 (-0.65 , 0.68)	-0.04 (-0.22 , 0.19)	2.46 (1.51 , 4.53)	0.17 (0.05 , 0.39)

Table 2.2. Ensemble mean frequency of moderate and severe productivity drought days (%) in the control time period, as well as the ensemble mean changes in the frequency of drought days (%) in the different time periods considered for the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Ensemble minimum and maximum values are given in brackets. Averages are computed over land. Blue (orange) colours indicate a drought decrease (increase) in the scenarios. The scenario changes are percentages with respect to the total number of days in the respective period, not with respect to the control value. Dark blue and orange colours, respectively, are applied to those cells in which ensemble minimum and maximum values have the same sign. Light blue and orange colours indicate the opposite.

Wind energy productivity:

From Figure 3.2.3_E2_A of deliverable 4.3, a general decrease can be observed for every scenario and period, being the 2081-2100 period in RCP8.5 the one with the highest decrease. A noticeable maximum decrease is observed between Mallorca and Ibiza in this latter case, while over land the decrease is smaller in absolute terms, but higher in relative terms as W_{prod} is systematically lower.

W_{prod} is systematically much higher over the sea, due to the fact that there is less friction than over land. This occurs in all areas of the domain. The future decrease in W_{prod} is found for both land and maritime regions and both emissions scenarios, although with differences in the magnitude. RCP8.5 is clearly the scenario where a higher decrease in productivity is expected. It is worth noting that RCP2.6 seems to recover from the decrease by the end of the 21st century, in contrast to RCP8.5. The decreases are higher in relative terms over land (up to 13%, Table 2.1).

The future decrease is quite robust as demonstrated by the uncertainty analysis. All models agree in the negative sign of the changes in most of the regions. This agreement is complete in 2081-2100 period in RCP8.5 (Figure 3.2.3_E2_B). The spatially averaged changes confirm the robustness of the decrease, showing no uncertainty in the sign among models (Table 2.1). The general decrease obtained in this region is consistent previous studies (Tobin et al., 2015, 2016).

Photovoltaic energy productivity:

There is a general decrease in photovoltaic productivity for the Balearic Islands with respect to the control period (1986-2005) that can be seen in their spatial representation in Figure 3.2.3_E1_A (Deliverable 4.3). The most negative changes can be found in RCP8.5 scenario at the end of the century (2081-2100). The photovoltaic productivity decrease is larger over the sea than over land. Uncertainty in the sign of the projected changes in future scenarios is low, with a general agreement except for RCP2.6 over land, where one of the models project a positive change. Changes are rather small in scenario RCP2.6 (around 1%), while in scenario RCP8.5 a decrease of 2% (land) and 5% (sea) is projected at the end of the century (Table 2.1). These results agree with previous references that project a slight decrease of PV production over the south of Europe (Jerez et al., 2015).

Energy productivity droughts:

Wind productivity droughts are more prone to occur over land than over the sea (Figure 3.2.3_E3.1_A). Wind droughts experience a generalised increase in frequency in all scenarios and time periods considered (see also Table 2.2). The increase in the occurrence of wind droughts is especially remarkable in the second half of the 21st century, in the RCP8.5 scenario, where moderate droughts occur on average for 17 days more per year and severe droughts for 13 days more per year. The increase in the occurrence of wind droughts in the RCP8.5 scenario is a robust result since most of the models that conform the ensemble predict an increase in the frequency of droughts (see Figure 3.2.3_E3.1_B). The obtained results are consistent with the projected drop in wind productivity commented above.

Regarding moderate PV droughts, we observe that these are much less frequent than wind droughts, with values smaller than 10% of the days (Figure 3.2.3_E4.1_A and Table 2.2). Moderate PV droughts experience a subtle increase over the sea in the RCP8.5 case with a minor

decrease to the north of Mallorca. An increase in the frequency of moderate PV droughts is projected for RCP8.5 over the sea, which is in line with the observed drop in PV productivity (Figure 3.2.3_E1_A). The very low values of severe PV droughts in the control period almost do no change in any of the scenarios and periods. In all cases, drought frequencies and their changes are much smaller for PV than for wind energy, indicating that PV energy is much more reliable than wind energy. This positive aspect of PV is reflected in the results for the combined PV and wind energy scenario: in the control period, the moderate drought frequency is much nearer to the PV moderate drought frequency, and the severe drought frequency (only 2 days per year) is almost negligible, even below the one for PV energy (4 days per year). In contrast, there are more than 100 days per year of severe wind drought. This positive effect of the combination is likely due to the complementarity of PV and wind for these islands.

3.1.3 Baltic Islands

<i>Baltic Islands</i>		<i>Wind Energy Prod</i>		<i>PV Prod</i>	
		<i>Land</i>	<i>Sea</i>	<i>Land</i>	<i>Sea</i>
<i>CTRL</i>	<i>1986-2005</i>	2735 (2458 , 3014)	4432 (4186 , 4681)	1147 (1116 , 1210)	1164 (1140 , 1220)
<i>RCP2.6</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	-78 (-92 , -64)	-94 (-101 , -87)	-27 (-38 , -15)	-26 (-36 , -16)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	-136 (-261 , -12)	-162 (-301 , -23)	-16 (-26 , -5)	-16 (-27 , -5)
<i>RCP8.5</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	7 (-117 , 218)	70 (-125 , 359)	-62 (-79 , -47)	-59 (-71 , -49)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	27 (-176 , 143)	43 (-143 , 152)	-111 (-141 , -82)	-110 (-137 , -87)

Table 3.1. Ensemble mean values of annual wind and solar productivity indicators (kWh/kW) in the control period (1986-2005) and ensemble mean changes in future periods (2046-2065, 2081-2100) for the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Ensemble minimum and maximum values are shown in brackets. Spatial averages are computed for land and sea separately. Blue (orange) colours indicate the positive (negative) changes in the scenarios relative to the control period. Dark blue and orange colours, respectively, are applied to those cells in which ensemble minimum and maximum values have the same sign. Light blue and orange colours indicate the opposite.

<i>Baltic Islands</i>		<i>Wind</i>		<i>PV</i>		<i>Combined PV and Wind</i>	
		<i>Moderate</i>	<i>Severe</i>	<i>Moderate</i>	<i>Severe</i>	<i>Moderate</i>	<i>Severe</i>
<i>CTRL</i>	<i>1986-2005</i>	43.2 (41.7 , 45.0)	24.2 (22.3 , 25.6)	23.4 (21.7 , 24.8)	9.6 (8.0 , 10.5)	22.0 (19.9 , 24.0)	2.5 (2.9 , 2.2)
<i>RCP2.6</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	0.88 (0.35 , 1.41)	0.67 (0.02 , 1.31)	0.73 (-0.09 , 1.55)	0.26 (-0.00 , 0.53)	1.62 (1.39 , 1.84)	0.11 (-0.08 , 0.30)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	1.75 (0.73 , 2.78)	1.66 (1.02 , 2.30)	0.52 (-0.26 , 1.30)	0.33 (-0.41 , 1.07)	2.33 (1.35 , 3.31)	0.58 (0.23 , 0.92)
<i>RCP8.5</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	-0.69 (-3.69 , 1.77)	-0.38 (-2.18 , 1.56)	2.66 (2.04 , 3.53)	1.80 (1.01 , 2.45)	1.55 (-0.04 , 3.43)	0.34 (0.04 , 0.58)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	-0.13 (-1.50 , 2.10)	0.52 (-0.55 , 2.80)	5.00 (3.49 , 7.18)	3.47 (2.63 , 4.37)	3.15 (2.66 , 4.49)	0.62 (0.50 , 0.85)

Table 3.2. Ensemble mean frequency of moderate and severe productivity drought days (%) in the control time period, as well as the ensemble mean changes in the frequency of drought days (%) in the different time periods considered for the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Ensemble minimum and maximum values are given in brackets. Averages are computed over land. Blue (orange) colours indicate a drought decrease (increase) in the scenarios. The scenario changes are percentages with respect to the total number of days in the respective period, not with respect to the control value. Dark blue and orange colours, respectively, are applied to those cells in which ensemble minimum and maximum values have the same sign. Light blue and orange colours indicate the opposite.

Wind energy productivity:

Clear differences between scenarios can be observed (Figure 3.3.3_E2_A). RCP2.6 shows a general decrease in both periods, but RCP8.5 shows no changes or even slight increases in the 2046-2065 period, mainly over the sea. This increase over the sea is detected with certain agreement between models as derived from the uncertainty analysis (Figure 3.3.3_E2_B), while there is a clearer coincidence among models for the decrease found in RCP2.6. The fact that this region has no clear signal in changes, as opposed to the Mediterranean regions, is consistent with previous studies (Tobin et al., 2015, 2016).

W_{prod} averaged over the region (Table 3.1) is consistent with the previous analysis, where the behaviour of RCP8.5 is different from RCP2.6. RCP8.5 results in small increases of W_{prod} both over land and sea (less than 2% of the respective productivity in the control period), although the agreement between models is low, while the decrease for RCP2.6 is consistent in sign among models and reaches 5% over land at the end of the century.

Photovoltaic energy productivity:

A general decrease is projected over the Baltic Islands for each period of both scenarios (RCP2.6 and RCP8.5), with higher negative values for the period at the end of the century (2081-2100) in the RCP8.5 scenario, as can be seen in the Figure_3.3.3_E1_A in the Annex of this deliverable. In mean, these are comparatively high changes, decreasing by around 10% the control period productivity in RCP8.5 scenario at the end of the century. The projected decrease in RCP2.6 scenario is clearly smaller, of around 2% in 2046-2065 period and around 1% in 2081-2100. The differences between sea and land mean values are small.

Changes found over the Baltic Islands in the RCP8.5 scenario are more noticeable than changes found for Mediterranean Islands. Previous studies show also such a decrease in projected PV power and surface solar radiation, and associate it to more intense, frequent or persistent positive North Atlantic Oscillation phases (Jerez et al., 2015, Bartok et al., 2017).

Energy productivity droughts:

In the control time period, wind droughts are much more likely to occur over land than over the sea (Figure 3.3.3_E3.1_A). The frequency of days in which wind drought conditions develop increases in the RCP2.6 scenario, while the frequency of wind droughts goes down in the RCP8.5 case. Only severe wind droughts show an increase to the southwest of the domain, in the RCP8.5 scenario, at the end of the 21st century (see also Table 3.2). The increase in the percentage of days with wind drought conditions in the RCP2.6 scenario is supported by most of the models considered in the ensemble (Figure 3.3.3_E3.1_B). Changes in the frequency of wind droughts are in line with changes in the wind productivity in the corresponding scenarios and time periods (Figure_3.3.3_E2_A). PV droughts are clearly more frequent than in most of the other studied regions, with values for moderate droughts close to 23% over land (Table 3.2). In all scenarios and time periods, the frequency of PV droughts increases. This rise is more remarkable in the 2081-2100 time period of the RCP8.5 scenario, where increases of 18 days per year of moderate droughts and 13 days per year of severe droughts are projected. There is no uncertainty at all in

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the sign of this change (Figure 3.3.3_E4.1_B). It is remarkable that, in this case, changes in the frequency of severe droughts have a similar magnitude to changes in the occurrence of moderate droughts. The effect of combining PV and wind energy is particularly positive for reducing droughts, as severe combined droughts are much lower than severe PV droughts in the control period.

3.1.4 Canary Islands

Canary Islands		Wind Energy Prod		PV Prod	
		Land	Sea	Land	Sea
CTRL	1986-2005	4083 (4043 , 4155)	5824 (5710 , 5890)	1533 (1506 , 1572)	1484 (1465 , 1502)
RCP2.6	2046-2065	16 (16 , 16)	-7 (-7 , -7)	2 (2 , 2)	-13 (-13 , -13)
	2081-2100	-83 (-83 , -83)	-64 (-64 , -64)	-10 (-10 , -10)	-17 (-17 , -17)
RCP8.5	2046-2065	89 (54 , 130)	60 (-5 , 112)	3 (-10 , 15)	-24 (-28 , -22)
	2081-2100	195 (92 , 282)	118 (-9 , 253)	1 (-6 , 16)	-51 (-51 , -51)

Table 4.1. Ensemble mean values of annual wind and solar productivity indicators (kWh/kW) in the control period (1986-2005) and ensemble mean changes in future periods (2046-2065, 2081-2100) for the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Ensemble minimum and maximum values are shown in brackets. Spatial averages are computed for land and sea separately. Blue (orange) colours indicate the positive (negative) changes in the scenarios relative to the control period. Dark blue and orange colours, respectively, are applied to those cells in which ensemble minimum and maximum values have the same sign. Light blue and orange colours indicate the opposite.

Canary Islands		Wind		PV		Combined PV and Wind	
		Moderate	Severe	Moderate	Severe	Moderate	Severe
CTRL	1986-2005	30.9 (29.0 , 32.0)	15.3 (13.9 , 16.2)	5.6 (5.1 , 6.5)	0.2 (0.1 , 0.3)	21.4 (19.6 , 22.7)	1.2 (0.9 , 1.6)
RCP2.6	2046-2065	-0.84 (-0.84 , -0.84)	-1.36 (-1.36 , -1.36)	-0.18 (-0.18 , -0.18)	-0.10 (-0.10 , -0.10)	-1.11 (-1.11 , -1.11)	-0.09 (-0.09 , -0.09)
	2081-2100	0.61 (0.61 , 0.61)	-0.56 (-0.56 , -0.56)	0.14 (0.14 , 0.14)	-0.01 (-0.01 , -0.01)	0.14 (0.14 , 0.14)	0.12 (0.12 , 0.12)
RCP8.5	2046-2065	-1.88 (-3.11 , -0.90)	-1.73 (-2.55 , -1.21)	-0.94 (-1.68 , -0.40)	0.01 (-0.11 , 0.09)	-1.54 (-1.92 , -1.03)	-0.20 (-0.38 , -0.01)
	2081-2100	-3.18 (-5.28 , -1.16)	-2.76 (-4.12 , -1.79)	-1.48 (-2.24 , -0.50)	-0.05 (-0.17 , 0.06)	-2.86 (-4.72 , -1.68)	-0.51 (-0.83 , -0.26)

Table 4.2. Ensemble mean frequency of moderate and severe productivity drought days (%) in the control time period, as well as the ensemble mean changes in the frequency of drought days (%) in the different time periods considered for the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Ensemble minimum and maximum values are given in brackets. Averages are computed over land. Blue (orange) colours indicate a drought decrease (increase) in the scenarios. The scenario changes are percentages with respect to the total number of days in the respective period, not with respect to the control value. Dark blue and orange colours, respectively, are applied to those cells in which ensemble minimum and maximum values have the same sign. Light blue and orange colours indicate the opposite.

Wind energy productivity:

Clear differences can be observed between scenarios (Figure 3.4.3_E2_A). While RCP8.5 points to an important increase in W_{prod} , especially in the 2081-2100 period, RCP2.6 scenario shows even a slight decrease at the end of the 21st century. Table 4.1 shows that W_{prod} (spatially averaged over land and sea points) is particularly large, in comparison with other islands. Changes are generally small with respect to control values. The largest change is found over land at the end of the century in RCP8.5 scenario, with an increase of nearly 5%.

Photovoltaic energy productivity:

Figure_3.4.3_E1_A from Deliverable 4.3 shows the spatial structure of the ensemble mean values of photovoltaic productivity in the control period (1986-2005), and changes for the future periods at mid and the end of the century (2046-2065 and 2081-2100 respectively) for the two different scenarios. In general, eastern islands have higher productivity values, while lower values are seen on the north-west side of the domain. A decrease in photovoltaic productivity is predominantly projected for both scenarios and each period, although more negative values can be found in the 2081-2100 period for the RCP8.5 scenario. The decrease is more noticeable for the southern part of the domain in 2081-2100 period and the RCP8.5 scenario. One important feature of the spatial structure is that changes are less negative and slightly positive in some cases over land, whereas they are negative over the sea, as indicated in Table 4.1. The spatially averaged changes are anyway small, around 1% in most cases, except over the sea in RCP8.5 at the end of the century, when the decrease could be about 3%.

Previous studies (Pérez et al., 2019), using climate simulations with a higher horizontal resolution have shown an increase over the Canary Islands for daily productivity in winter months, and no changes in summer daily productivity (at the end of the 21st century). That result is consistent with results presented here, where no changes or slightly positive changes are projected over land, which is due to the most important contribution of summer productivity to the annual computation.

Energy productivity droughts:

In the control time period, wind droughts are more frequent over the islands than over the sea (Figure 3.4.3_E3.1_A). Changes in wind productivity droughts in the RCP2.6 scenario present a large regional variability over the domain. In the RCP8.5 case, however, the frequency of wind productivity droughts shows an important decrease, especially in second half of the 21st century (see also Table 4.2). This decrease in the frequency of wind droughts in the RCP8.5 scenario over the studied domain is supported by most of the models from the ensemble, especially over the islands (Figure 3.4.3_E3.1_B) and is in line with the increase of wind productivity (Table 4.1). PV droughts are much less frequent than wind droughts over the region of study (see Figure 3.4.3_E4.1_A). As for moderate wind droughts, changes in the frequency of moderate PV droughts show great spatial variability in the RCP2.6 case, while a generalised decrease in the occurrence of moderate PV droughts is found for the RCP8.5 scenario. This reduction in the frequency of moderate PV droughts in the RCP8.5 scenario is supported by most of the models from the ensemble (Figure 3.4.3_E4.1_B). Interestingly, in this case, PV productivity decreases

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over most of the marine regions where moderate PV droughts become less frequent (Figure 3.4.3_E1_A). Regarding severe PV droughts, their frequency in the control period and their changes are very small in both scenarios (Table 4.1). In the combined PV and wind energy scenario, a strong reduction in frequency is found for severe droughts in the control period in comparison to the severe wind droughts.

3.1.5 Corsica

Corsica		Wind Energy Prod		PV Prod	
		Land	Sea	Land	Sea
<i>CTRL</i>	<i>1986-2005</i>	2242 (1863 , 2482)	3963 (3623 , 4213)	1522 (1527 , 1590)	1509 (1487 , 1549)
<i>RCP2.6</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	65 (14 , 116)	25 (-19 , 69)	-20 (-33 , -7)	-23 (-31 , -13)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	41 (-3 , 86)	49 (40 , 58)	-22 (-45 , 1)	-19 (-35 , -4)
<i>RCP8.5</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	-8 (-50 , 27)	-68 (-119 , 9)	-18 (-33 , -2)	-35 (-45 , -14)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	-70 (-140 , 16)	-192 (-274 , -157)	-25 (-40 , -7)	-66 (-71 , -36)

Table 5.1. Ensemble mean values of annual wind and solar productivity indicators (kWh/kW) in the control period (1986-2005) and ensemble mean changes in future periods (2046-2065, 2081-2100) for the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Ensemble minimum and maximum values are shown in brackets. Spatial averages are computed for land and sea separately. Blue (orange) colours indicate the positive (negative) changes in the scenarios relative to the control period. Dark blue and orange colours, respectively, are applied to those cells in which ensemble minimum and maximum values have the same sign. Light blue and orange colours indicate the opposite.

Corsica		Wind		PV		Combined PV and Wind	
		Moderate	Severe	Moderate	Severe	Moderate	Severe
<i>CTRL</i>	<i>1986-2005</i>	55.1 (53.1 , 57.3)	39.5 (37.3 , 40.8)	10.2 (9.12 , 11.5)	2.8 (2.5 , 3.2)	21.0 (16.2 , 24.8)	1.1 (0.9 , 1.3)
<i>RCP2.6</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	-0.62 (-1.47 , 0.23)	-0.50 (-1.40 , 0.40)	0.53 (-0.14 , 1.21)	0.36 (0.11 , 0.61)	0.18 (0.04 , 0.33)	-0.05 (-0.11 , 0.02)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	-0.24 (-0.97 , 0.49)	0.16 (-0.63 , 0.96)	0.39 (-0.80 , 1.58)	0.20 (-0.31 , 0.71)	0.84 (0.07 , 1.62)	0.01 (-0.23 , 0.25)
<i>RCP8.5</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	0.94 (0.42 , 1.44)	0.99 (0.15 , 1.40)	0.16 (-0.36 , 0.47)	0.37 (0.04 , 0.57)	1.26 (0.71 , 1.64)	-0.01 (-0.06 , 0.08)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	2.62 (1.59 , 4.44)	2.78 (1.56 , 4.64)	-0.43 (-1.20 , -0.04)	0.19 (-0.18 , 0.39)	2.88 (1.97 , 4.10)	0.05 (-0.06 , 0.18)

Table 5.2. Ensemble mean frequency of moderate and severe productivity drought days (%) in the control time period, as well as the ensemble mean changes in the frequency of drought days (%) in the different time periods considered for the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Ensemble minimum and maximum values are given in brackets. Averages are computed over land. Blue (orange) colours indicate a drought decrease (increase) in the scenarios. The scenario changes are percentages with respect to the total number of days in the respective period, not with respect to the control value. Dark blue and orange colours, respectively, are applied to those cells in which ensemble minimum and maximum values have the same sign. Light blue and orange colours indicate the opposite.

Wind energy productivity:

An important decrease of W_{prod} (Figure 3.5.3_E2_A of deliverable 4.3) is obtained in RCP8.5 at the end of this century, specially over the sea, where it reaches 5% in spatial average (Table 5.1). In RCP2.6 changes are small. These general trends are affected by regional differences, probably related to orography-wind interaction. The decrease in RCP8.5 is robustly supported by the uncertainty analysis, except for those regions where the decrease is weaker. Tobin et al. (2015, 2016) also show a general decrease with noticeable regional differences. Model spread is relatively high, with differences in the sign of changes in several cases (Table 5.1).

Photovoltaic energy productivity:

A decrease is projected for Corsica in both scenarios and each period, but its magnitude is generally small, below or about 2% in all cases except in scenario RCP8.5 at the end of the century where the projected decrease reaches 4% over the sea (Table 5.1). Differences between land and sea are not very high, although spatially averaged values of changes over the sea are more negative. The spatial distribution (Figure_3.5.3_E1_A) shows that some positive changes appear over Corsica for 2081-2100 period in the RCP8.5 scenario, although their magnitude is small.

Energy productivity droughts:

In the control time period, moderate and severe wind droughts are more prone to occur than in most of the other islands, especially over land, where moderate droughts develop about 55% of the days (Figure 3.5.3_E3.1_A and Table 5.2). This indicates that wind is highly variable, with extended periods of low wind. In the RCP2.6 scenario, wind droughts mostly decrease in frequency, but changes are small, whilst in the RCP8.5 scenario the droughts become more frequent. The increase in the percentage of wind droughts is particularly remarkable over land, in the second half of the 21st century, in the RCP8.5 scenario. The increase in the frequency of wind droughts observed in the RCP8.5 scenario in the 2081-2100 time period is well supported by most of the models that conform the ensemble (Figure 3.5.3_E3.1_B), as well as by changes in the wind productivity (Table 5.1). PV droughts are more frequent over land than over the sea in the control period (Figure_3.5.3_E4.1_A). In particular, the western portion of the island is more prone to experience PV droughts. In the RCP2.6 scenario, moderate PV droughts show a subtle increase in occurrence over the land and the sea. However, in the RCP8.5 scenario, moderate PV droughts decrease over land in the 2081-2100 time period. Interestingly, the sharpest decrease occurs to the west of the island, where PV droughts in the control are more frequent. The latter finding is supported by many models from the ensemble (Figure 3.5.3_E4.1_B) and is in line with changes observed in PV productivity (Figure_3.5.3_E1_A). Severe droughts tend to experience a small increase in occurrence regardless of the scenario considered. The combination of PV and wind energy has a strong positive effect on severe droughts, which are reduced even below the rather small value of PV severe droughts in the control time period.

3.1.6 Crete

Crete		Wind Energy Prod		PV Prod	
		Land	Sea	Land	Sea
CTRL	1986-2005	2559 (2496 , 2634)	4592 (4529 , 4643)	1584 (1539 , 1633)	1565 (1535 , 1589)
RCP2.6	2046-2065	160 (129 , 191)	107 (61 , 153)	1 (-4 , 7)	-15 (-24 , -7)
	2081-2100	71 (70 , 71)	59 (2 , 116)	-4 (-10 , 2)	-17 (-24 , -11)
RCP8.5	2046-2065	118 (-22 , 234)	65 (-37 , 161)	-13 (-20 , -8)	-36 (-45 , -20)
	2081-2100	136 (-16 , 267)	14 (-83 , 90)	-16 (-35 , 8)	-66 (-80 , -52)

Table 6.1. Ensemble mean values of annual wind and solar productivity indicators (kWh/kW) in the control period (1986-2005) and ensemble mean changes in future periods (2046-2065, 2081-2100) for the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Ensemble minimum and maximum values are shown in brackets. Spatial averages are computed for land and sea separately. Blue (orange) colours indicate the positive (negative) changes in the scenarios relative to the control period. Dark blue and orange colours, respectively, are applied to those cells in which ensemble minimum and maximum values have the same sign. Light blue and orange colours indicate the opposite.

Crete		Wind		PV		Combined PV and Wind	
		Moderate	Severe	Moderate	Severe	Moderate	Severe
CTRL	1986-2005	46.2 (45.1 , 46.7)	28.8 (28.1 , 29.2)	8.7 (7.5 , 9.6)	1.2 (0.9 , 1.4)	22.7 (21.8 , 24.3)	1.5 (1.3 , 1.6)
RCP2.6	2046-2065	-1.84 (-2.88 , -0.80)	-1.13 (-1.63 , -0.63)	-0.62 (-0.89 , -0.34)	-0.14 (-0.22 , -0.05)	-0.61 (-1.68 , 0.45)	-0.09 (-0.20 , 0.02)
	2081-2100	-0.76 (-0.93 , -0.60)	-0.39 (-0.59 , -0.18)	-0.33 (-0.36 , -0.29)	-0.04 (-0.09 , 0.01)	0.06 (-0.53 , 0.65)	0.02 (-0.24 , 0.29)
RCP8.5	2046-2065	-1.42 (-2.84 , 0.40)	-0.74 (-1.76 , 0.27)	-0.12 (-0.62 , 0.28)	0.05 (-0.08 , 0.17)	0.15 (-0.95 , 1.57)	-0.02 (-0.19 , 0.13)
	2081-2100	-1.23 (-2.84 , 0.90)	-0.50 (-1.16 , 1.15)	-1.02 (-1.99 , 0.18)	-0.06 (-0.38 , 0.20)	1.23 (0.06 , 2.32)	0.01 (-0.10 , 0.11)

Table 6.2. Ensemble mean frequency of moderate and severe productivity drought days (%) in the control time period, as well as the ensemble mean changes in the frequency of drought days (%) in the different time periods considered for the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Ensemble minimum and maximum values are given in brackets. Averages are computed over land. Blue (orange) colours indicate a drought decrease (increase) in the scenarios. The scenario changes are percentages with respect to the total number of days in the respective period, not with respect to the control value. Dark blue and orange colours, respectively, are applied to those cells in which ensemble minimum and maximum values have the same sign. Light blue and orange colours indicate the opposite.

Wind energy productivity:

Important regional differences can be observed, which could be related to the complex orography of Crete. Within this complex context, increases of W_{prod} tend to prevail in the 2046-2065 period for both RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 (Figure 3.6.3_E2_A). On the contrary, W_{prod} decreases tend to be spatially more extended in the 2081-2100 period. RCP8.5 scenario shows a complex pattern of maxima and minima, with decreases prevailing to the south and northwest of the island, and maxima located inland. The maximum relative change is about 6% in spatial average over land for mid-century period in RCP2.6 (Table 6.1). With respect to the uncertainty analysis (Figure 3.6.3_E2_B), there is agreement among models in the increase projected in the RCP2.6 scenario in the mid-century period over most of the domain. The complex patterns of W_{prod} change, projected in RCP8.5, are also visible in the uncertainty analysis. This makes the RCP8.5 change uncertain in sign in spatial average, both over land and sea (Table 6.1). The different behaviour of this region with respect to the central and western part of the Mediterranean Sea is also a noteworthy result found in Tobin et al. (2015, 2016), where increases in W_{prod} are found in the Aegean Sea, which affect Crete Island.

Photovoltaic energy productivity:

The ensemble mean value in photovoltaic productivity (Figure_3.6.3_E1_A) show spatial differences mostly over the Crete Island, which probably is due to its complex orography. That can be also appreciated in mean changes maps, where the sign of changes in some regions over land are positive, in contrast with the mean value of the whole domain. There is high agreement among models in the sign of changes for most of the areas (see Figure_3.6.3_E1_B of deliverable 4.3), but the spatial differences cause a small and uncertain change in spatial average over land in RCP2.6 (Table 6.1), so that spatially averaged values over land are close to zero, while over the sea they represent a 1% decrease with respect to the control period. For the RCP8.5 scenario, changes are bigger, with the same pattern: more negative on average over sea than over land but still under 5% with respect to the control period.

The small magnitude of the projected changes is in line with the study of Panagea et al. (2014), in which where a small increase in simulated photovoltaic production was projected over Crete in simulations for SRES A1B emissions scenario. In that study, the increase in surface solar radiation was partly compensated by the increase in projected temperature.

Energy productivity droughts:

The frequency of moderate and severe wind droughts is, in the control time period, systematically higher over the land than over the sea (Figure 3.6.3_E3.1_A). In the RCP2.6 scenario, an overall reduction of the percentage of days that feature wind drought conditions is observed over the studied domain. In the RCP8.5 scenario, in contrast, the frequency of wind droughts goes down within the island, but increases over the marine areas adjacent to it, especially to the south. Changes in wind productivity are generally consistent with projected changes in wind productivity for the different scenarios and time periods (Figure_3.6.3_E2_A and Tables 6.1-6.2). Addressing PV droughts, both their frequency in the control period and their future changes are smaller than for wind droughts (Table 6.2). We observe that in the control period, the

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northwest of the island is more prone to experience PV droughts (Figure 3.6.3_E4.1_A). Moderate PV droughts tend to decrease in frequency in the RCP2.6 scenario whilst, in the RCP8.5 case, they become less frequent over land but more likely to develop over the sea, but in general the changes are rather small. Projected changes in the frequency of severe PV droughts are almost zero. The impact of combining PV and wind energy is really positive for severe droughts, as their frequency is much smaller than for wind energy alone.

3.1.7 Cyprus

Cyprus		Wind Energy Prod		PV Prod	
		Land	Sea	Land	Sea
<i>CTRL</i>	<i>1986-2005</i>	1435 (1367 , 1477)	3245 (3069 , 3326)	1615 (1560 , 1666)	1559 (1518 , 1590)
<i>RCP2.6</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	25 (-55 , 104)	11 (-135 , 157)	-4 (-9 , 1)	-14 (-17 , -11)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	-41 (-66 , -17)	-13 (-101 , 75)	-6 (-6 , -6)	-16 (-17 , -15)
<i>RCP8.5</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	-45 (-103 , 19)	-96 (-176 , -21)	-13 (-19 , -4)	-36 (-48 , -16)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	-140 (-254 , -63)	-283 (-431 , -100)	-23 (-35 , -6)	-68 (-93 , -51)

Table 7.1. Ensemble mean values of annual wind and solar productivity indicators (kWh/kW) in the control period (1986-2005) and ensemble mean changes in future periods (2046-2065, 2081-2100) for the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Ensemble minimum and maximum values are shown in brackets. Spatial averages are computed for land and sea separately. Blue (orange) colours indicate the positive (negative) changes in the scenarios relative to the control period. Dark blue and orange colours, respectively, are applied to those cells in which ensemble minimum and maximum values have the same sign. Light blue and orange colours indicate the opposite.

Cyprus		Wind		PV		Combined PV and Wind	
		Moderate	Severe	Moderate	Severe	Moderate	Severe
<i>CTRL</i>	<i>1986-2005</i>	51.0 (50.1 , 53.5)	27.6 (26.7 , 29.1)	6.4 (5.2 , 7.3)	0.8 (0.6 , 1.0)	7.9 (7.2 , 8.7)	0.4 (0.3 , 0.4)
<i>RCP2.6</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	-0.22 (-1.92 , 1.49)	-0.37 (-1.30 , 0.56)	-0.54 (-1.42 , 0.34)	-0.12 (-0.25 , 0.01)	-0.29 (-0.29 , -0.28)	-0.04 (-0.06 , -0.02)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	0.59 (0.55 , 0.62)	0.46 (0.37 , 0.56)	-0.55 (-0.76 , -0.35)	-0.12 (-0.18 , -0.07)	0.14 (-0.19 , 0.46)	-0.04 (-0.08 , 0.01)
<i>RCP8.5</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	1.54 (0.32 , 3.08)	0.64 (-0.39 , 1.94)	-0.58 (-0.99 , -0.29)	-0.04 (-0.12 , 0.07)	-0.04 (-0.46 , 0.64)	-0.05 (-0.13 , 0.01)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	4.38 (0.48 , 9.00)	2.38 (-0.67 , 5.74)	-1.28 (-1.79 , -0.53)	-0.20 (-0.39 , -0.05)	0.47 (0.01 , 1.45)	0.00 (-0.09 , 0.09)

Table 7.2. Ensemble mean frequency of moderate and severe productivity drought days (%) in the control time period, as well as the ensemble mean changes in the frequency of drought days (%) in the different time periods considered for the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Ensemble minimum and maximum values are given in brackets. Averages are computed over land. Blue (orange) colours indicate a drought decrease (increase) in the scenarios. The scenario changes are percentages with respect to the total number of days in the respective period, not with respect to the control value. Dark blue and orange colours, respectively, are applied to those cells in which ensemble minimum and maximum values have the same sign. Light blue and orange colours indicate the opposite.

Wind energy productivity:

No important changes are obtained for both RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios in the 2046-2065 period (Figure 3.7.3_E2_A), except for a certain decrease over the sea in RCP8.5 of 3% in spatial average (Table 7.1). However, at the end of the century, both RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 indicate a decrease in W_{prod} , which is more pronounced in the RCP8.5 scenario, specially over the sea (nearly 9% in spatial average). The uncertainty analysis (Figure 3.7.3_E2_B) is quite robust in the latter, but models diverge in their response in the rest of the cases, with important regional differences in RCP8.5 (2046-2065). Model spread is high (Table 7.1), with one model projecting a spatially averaged decrease of 13% over sea and nearly 18% over land in RCP8.5 at the end of the century. Other studies seem to also show a general decrease in this region (Tobin et al., 2015, 2016).

Photovoltaic energy productivity:

As in the case of Crete, spatial differences between areas of the Cyprus Island can be appreciated in Figure_3.7.3_E1_A of deliverable 4.3, with minimum values in mountain regions. Changes in future periods are also different for that areas in comparison with the maritime area, where a generalised decrease is projected. Although some positive changes are seen over land in some areas, especially for the RCP8.5 scenario at the end of the century, spatially averaged changes over land are negative, although they are very small (less than 2%, see Table 7.1). The higher decrease is projected also for the RCP8.5 scenario at the end of the century over the sea. In spatial average, it represents a 4% negative change (Table 7.1).

Energy productivity droughts:

Wind productivity droughts in the control period are quite frequent, especially to the west of the island (Figure 3.7.3_E3.1_A). In the RCP2.6 scenario, changes in the frequency of wind droughts show great spatial variability over the considered domain. In the RCP8.5 case, there is a sharp increase in the number of drought days in all regions except for the marine areas immediately to the north and to the south of the island. The increase observed in the RCP8.5 scenario in the 2081-2100 time period is greater than 4% of all days (about 16 days more per year) for moderate droughts over land (Table 7.2) and is supported by most of the models from the ensemble (Figure 3.7.3_E3.1_B). Changes in the occurrence of wind droughts are roughly consistent with changes observed in wind productivity (Figure_3.7.3_E2_A). PV droughts are much less frequent than wind droughts in the control period. They are also more prone to develop over the west of the island (Figure 3.7.3_E4.1_A). Interestingly, a general decrease in the frequency of moderate PV droughts is projected in both scenarios. This decrease is particularly remarkable for moderate droughts in the RCP8.5 scenario and this response is supported (over the west of the island) by most of the ensemble models, especially in the 2081-2100 period (Figure 3.7.3_E4.1_B). Severe PV droughts are already very infrequent in the control period (about 3 days per year) and tend to experience very little changes with a minor decrease over localised areas. The combination of PV and wind energy has large positive effects on the drought frequency: the combined moderate drought frequency is 7 times smaller than the frequency for wind energy alone, and the combined severe drought frequency is practically zero, pointing to a high complementarity of wind and solar energy.

3.1.8 Madeira

<i>Madeira</i>		<i>Wind Energy Prod</i>		<i>PV Prod</i>	
		<i>Land</i>	<i>Sea</i>	<i>Land</i>	<i>Sea</i>
<i>CTRL</i>	<i>1986-2005</i>	3510 (3441 , 3590)	5407 (5253 , 5504)	1281 (1239 , 1340)	1300 (1278 , 1339)
<i>RCP2.6</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	-123 (-123 , -123)	-123 (-123 , -123)	-13 (-13 , -13)	-18 (-18 , -18)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	-143 (-143 , -143)	-143 (-143 , -143)	-25 (-25 , -25)	-24 (-24 , -24)
<i>RCP8.5</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	-72 (-132 , 15)	-18 (-77 , 83)	4 (-4 , 19)	-18 (-26 , -4)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	-81 (-122 , -35)	4 (-16 , 37)	13 (-4 , 44)	-33 (-45 , -12)

Table 8.1. Ensemble mean values of annual wind and solar productivity indicators (kWh/kW) in the control period (1986-2005) and ensemble mean changes in future periods (2046-2065, 2081-2100) for the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Ensemble minimum and maximum values are shown in brackets. Spatial averages are computed for land and sea separately. Blue (orange) colours indicate the positive (negative) changes in the scenarios relative to the control period. Dark blue and orange colours, respectively, are applied to those cells in which ensemble minimum and maximum values have the same sign. Light blue and orange colours indicate the opposite

<i>Madeira</i>		<i>Wind</i>		<i>PV</i>		<i>Combined PV and Wind</i>	
		<i>Moderate</i>	<i>Severe</i>	<i>Moderate</i>	<i>Severe</i>	<i>Moderate</i>	<i>Severe</i>
<i>CTRL</i>	<i>1986-2005</i>	36.6 (35.1 , 37.7)	19.4 (17.7 , 20.7)	11.1 (9.7 , 12.6)	1.3 (1.0 , 1.9)	25.6 (24.1 , 27.0)	1.9 (1.2 , 2.3)
<i>RCP2.6</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	1.67 (1.67 , 1.67)	2.05 (2.05 , 2.05)	0.83 (0.83 , 0.83)	0.03 (0.03 , 0.03)	2.71 (2.71 , 2.71)	0.53 (0.53 , 0.53)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	1.56 (1.56 , 1.56)	1.62 (1.62 , 1.62)	0.70 (0.70 , 0.70)	-0.01 (-0.01 , -0.01)	2.48 (2.48 , 2.48)	0.11 (0.11 , 0.11)
<i>RCP8.5</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	0.29 (-0.89 , 1.51)	-0.18 (-1.33 , 0.90)	-0.78 (-1.73 , -0.11)	-0.25 (-0.42 , -0.08)	0.54 (-0.38 , 2.35)	-0.14 (-0.30 , 0.12)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	0.14 (-0.63 , 0.96)	0.19 (-0.55 , 0.69)	-2.04 (-3.68 , -1.11)	-0.32 (-0.74 , -0.04)	0.27 (-1.08 , 1.22)	0.01 (-0.10 , 0.20)

Table 8.2. Ensemble mean frequency of moderate and severe productivity drought days (%) in the control time period, as well as the ensemble mean changes in the frequency of drought days (%) in the different time periods considered for the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Ensemble minimum and maximum values are given in brackets. Averages are computed over land. Blue (orange) colours indicate a drought decrease (increase) in the scenarios. The scenario changes are percentages with respect to the total number of days in the respective period, not with respect to the control value. Dark blue and orange colours, respectively, are applied to those cells in which ensemble minimum and maximum values have the same sign. Light blue and orange colours indicate the opposite.

Wind energy productivity:

Control period values are very high both over land and sea, in comparison to the other islands of the study (W_{prod} is only higher in the Canary Islands). A general trend to decreasing W_{prod} is obtained for almost all the cases, which is more important in RCP2.6 for 2081-2100 period (Figure 3.8.3_E2_A). The decreases are anyway smaller than 5% of the control period values (Table 8.1). However, a region of slight positive changes to the southeast of the island appears in RCP8.5 by 2081-2100, which is enough to cause a nearly zero spatially-averaged change over sea in this case. The projected changes in RCP8.5 are uncertain in sign (Figure 3.2.3_E2_B).

Photovoltaic energy productivity:

The annual mean value of photovoltaic productivity over Madeira in the control period (1986-2005) is lower than for the rest of Islands analysed in this project (except for the Azores, which presents values that should be taken with caution due to likely biases caused by their proximity to climate model boundaries). Solar irradiation values from EUMETSAT satellite over the Madeira Islands presents similar values than those for the north-western side of the Iberian Peninsula. Our computations over Madeira show values of PV productivity similar to those found in (Šúri et al., 2007) for their European solar potential publication.

Changes in photovoltaic productivity projected for this region are mostly negative but also rather small (less than 3% of the control period values, Table 8.1), and lower than the changes projected for other regions. An increase in photovoltaic productivity is projected over land for RCP8.5 scenario, although that increase represents just around 1% of the annual mean value. However, it is important to notice the coarse resolution of the model in comparison to the island area.

Energy productivity droughts:

In the control time period, wind productivity droughts are more prone to develop over land than over the sea (Figure 3.8.3_E3.1_A). Over the studied domain, the frequency of wind droughts tends to increase in the RCP2.6 scenario, while these present a subtle increase (decrease) to the north (south) of the domain in the RCP8.5 case. In the RCP8.5 scenario, models show agreement regarding the increase in the frequency of droughts observed to the north of the domain (Figure 3.8.3_E3.1_B). However, the decrease in the frequency of wind droughts projected to the south of the domain seems to be a less robust feature. In the case of PV droughts, we observe that moderate PV droughts tend to increase in frequency in the RCP2.6 scenario, but they decrease in the RCP8.5 case (Figure 3.8.3_E4.1_A and Table 8.2). The response found for the RCP8.5 scenario is more robust in the 2081-2100 time period (Figure 3.8.3_E4.1_B) and is in line with changes observed in PV productivity over land (Table 8.1). Severe PV droughts are very infrequent in the control period, and their projected changes are very small. The drought frequency for the combination of PV and wind energy is again very small for severe droughts, while moderate droughts maintain a rather high value (25.6% of all days) in the control period.

3.1.9 Malta

<i>Malta</i>		<i>Wind Energy Prod</i>		<i>PV Prod</i>	
		<i>Land</i>	<i>Sea</i>	<i>Land</i>	<i>Sea</i>
<i>CTRL</i>	<i>1986-2005</i>	2599 (2445 , 2741)	3836 (3712 , 4049)	1571 (1523 , 1623)	1525 (1493 , 1564)
<i>RCP2.6</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	-70 (-123 , -18)	-43 (-59 , -28)	-12 (-18 , -7)	-20 (-24 , -17)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	-39 (-134 , 57)	-26 (-74 , 23)	-10 (-22 , 3)	-16 (-26 , -9)
<i>RCP8.5</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	-100 (-211 , 9)	-109 (-175 , -53)	-30 (-44 , -16)	-44 (-55 , -23)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	-265 (-373 , -35)	-264 (-325 , -196)	-47 (-69 , -26)	-77 (-92 , -56)

Table 9.1. Ensemble mean values of annual wind and solar productivity indicators (kWh/kW) in the control period (1986-2005) and ensemble mean changes in future periods (2046-2065, 2081-2100) for the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Ensemble minimum and maximum values are shown in brackets. Spatial averages are computed for land and sea separately. Blue (orange) colours indicate the positive (negative) changes in the scenarios relative to the control period. Dark blue and orange colours, respectively, are applied to those cells in which ensemble minimum and maximum values have the same sign. Light blue and orange colours indicate the opposite.

<i>Malta</i>		<i>Wind</i>		<i>PV</i>		<i>Combined PV and Wind</i>	
		<i>Moderate</i>	<i>Severe</i>	<i>Moderate</i>	<i>Severe</i>	<i>Moderate</i>	<i>Severe</i>
<i>CTRL</i>	<i>1986-2005</i>	48.8 (46.6 , 50.9)	33.8 (31.0 , 36.3)	7.0 (5.3 , 8.1)	0.6 (0.3 , 0.8)	27.9 (27.6 , 28.3)	0.7 (0.6 , 0.9)
<i>RCP2.6</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	1.56 (0.88 , 2.24)	1.10 (0.65 , 1.55)	0.12 (-0.28 , 0.52)	-0.06 (-0.12 , -0.004)	1.87 (1.31 , 2.43)	0.00 (-0.07 , 0.07)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	0.92 (-0.31 , 2.16)	0.71 (0.15 , 1.27)	-0.13 (-0.62 , 0.37)	-0.13 (-0.16 , -0.09)	2.25 (1.18 , 3.31)	-0.06 (-0.34 , 0.22)
<i>RCP8.5</i>	<i>2046-2065</i>	2.30 (1.14 , 3.43)	2.02 (0.99 , 3.14)	0.41 (-0.57 , 1.07)	-0.02 (-0.16 , 0.05)	3.87 (2.55 , 4.86)	0.18 (-0.04 , 0.46)
	<i>2081-2100</i>	4.76 (2.96 , 6.80)	4.30 (2.78 , 5.82)	0.02 (-0.99 , 1.20)	-0.09 (-0.30 , 0.05)	7.55 (5.16 , 10.2)	0.37 (0.03 , 0.82)

Table 9.2. Ensemble mean frequency of moderate and severe productivity drought days (%) in the control time period, as well as the ensemble mean changes in the frequency of drought days (%) in the different time periods considered for the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Ensemble minimum and maximum values are given in brackets. Averages are computed over land. Blue (orange) colours indicate a drought decrease (increase) in the scenarios. The scenario changes are percentages with respect to the total number of days in the respective period, not with respect to the control value. Dark blue and orange colours, respectively, are applied to those cells in which ensemble minimum and maximum values have the same sign. Light blue and orange colours indicate the opposite.

For brevity, the main findings for this island are presented together with Sicily, by the end of this section.

3.1.10 Sardinia

Sardinia		Wind Energy Prod		PV Prod	
		Land	Sea	Land	Sea
CTRL	1986-2005	1967 (1677, 2105)	3963 (3623, 4213)	1533 (1501, 1582)	1509 (1487, 1549)
RCP2.6	2046-2065	27 (12, 43)	25 (-19, 69)	-10 (-18, -2)	-23 (-31, -13)
	2081-2100	14 (3, 26)	49 (40, 58)	-10 (-26, 7)	-19 (-35, -4)
RCP8.5	2046-2065	-9 (-58, 24)	-68 (-119, 9)	-8 (-26, 5)	-35 (-45, -14)
	2081-2100	-52 (-99, 6)	-192 (-274, -157)	-15 (-33, -3)	-66 (-71, -36)

Table 10.1. Ensemble mean values of wind and solar productivity indicators (kWh/kW) in the control period (1986-2005) and ensemble mean changes in future periods (2046-2065, 2081-2100) for the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Ensemble minimum and maximum values are shown in brackets. Spatial averages are computed for land and sea separately. Blue (orange) colours indicate the positive (negative) changes in the scenarios relative to the control period. Dark blue and orange colours, respectively, are applied to those cells in which ensemble minimum and maximum values have the same sign. Light blue and orange colours indicate the opposite.

Sardinia		Wind		PV		Combined PV and Wind	
		Moderate	Severe	Moderate	Severe	Moderate	Severe
CTRL	1986-2005	51.5 (49.9, 53.2)	31.8 (30.4, 32.8)	10.1 (8.9, 11.2)	1.8 (1.5, 2.2)	13.3 (11.2, 14.4)	0.6 (0.5, 0.8)
RCP2.6	2046-2065	-0.17 (-0.27, -0.07)	-0.01 (-0.18, 0.15)	0.31 (0.11, 0.50)	0.09 (-0.10, 0.29)	-0.22 (-0.33, -0.10)	0.02 (-0.04, 0.08)
	2081-2100	0.10 (-0.18, 0.38)	0.45 (0.38, 0.52)	0.04 (-0.71, 0.80)	0.01 (-0.29, 0.32)	0.23 (-0.76, 1.22)	0.00 (-0.20, 0.21)
RCP8.5	2046-2065	0.78 (0.14, 1.31)	0.68 (-0.28, 1.25)	-0.19 (-1.02, 0.39)	0.17 (-0.14, 0.41)	0.30 (-0.18, 1.19)	-0.04 (-0.09, 0.10)
	2081-2100	1.91 (0.83, 3.24)	1.65 (0.73, 2.83)	-0.91 (-1.51, -0.44)	-0.04 (-0.27, 0.07)	1.19 (0.20, 2.46)	0.03 (-0.09, 0.18)

Table 10.2. Ensemble mean frequency of moderate and severe productivity drought days (%) in the control time period, as well as the ensemble mean changes in the frequency of drought days (%) in the different time periods considered for the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Ensemble minimum and maximum values are given in brackets. Averages are computed over land. Blue (orange) colours indicate a drought decrease (increase) in the scenarios. The scenario changes are percentages with respect to the total number of days in the respective period, not with respect to the control value. Dark blue and orange colours, respectively, are applied to those cells in which ensemble minimum and maximum values have the same sign. Light blue and orange colours indicate the opposite.

Wind energy productivity:

Slight changes are obtained for RCP2.6 scenario and RCP8.5 by the middle of this century (Figure 3.10.3_E2_A). However, changes over the sea are larger in the RCP8.5 scenario by the end of the century, with a spatially averaged decrease of about 5% (Table 10.1). The uncertainty analysis shows a clear support for this last result, while regional differences point to more uncertain results in other cases (Figure 3.10.3_E2_B). Tobin et al. (2015, 2016) also show a general decrease with noticeable regional differences.

Photovoltaic energy productivity:

Spatial differences in photovoltaic productivity over the Sardinia Island can be appreciated in Figure_3.10.3_E1_A (deliverable 4.3). The “noisy” spatial pattern can be also seen in the projected changes, mostly for the period 2081-2100 in the RCP8.5 scenario. Areas with lower annual mean productivity over land present the highest increase in photovoltaic productivity for that scenario with an agreement of most of the models on that projection (Figure_3.10.3_E1_B). Despite of the local increase, in spatial average (Table 10.1) a decrease over land and on maritime areas is projected, as in all the other cases. However, the projected decrease is mostly small, with values that does not reach 1% of change over land, and changes over the sea with a maximum average that represents less than 5% of the annual mean productivity in the control period.

Energy productivity droughts:

In this region, in the control period, wind droughts are more frequent over land than over the sea, especially in the central and eastern portions of the island (Figure 3.10.3_E3.1_A). Changes in the frequency of wind droughts are rather small in the RCP2.6 scenario. In the RCP8.5 case, an increase in the occurrence of wind droughts is projected, reaching 7 days more per year for moderate droughts at the end of the century (Table 10.2). It is also remarkable that the greatest increase in the percentage of days in which drought conditions develop occurs in the center-east of the island, where droughts in the control time period are more likely to happen. The increase in the occurrence of wind droughts projected for the RCP8.5 scenario is supported by most of the ensemble models and therefore can be regarded as a robust result (Figure 3.10.3_E3.1_B). Changes in the frequency of wind droughts are in line with changes in wind productivity (Tables 10.1-10.2; see also Figure 3.10.3_E2_A). Regarding PV droughts, we observe that these are more frequent over land than over the sea, especially over the central and western sectors of the island (Figure 3.10.3_E4.1_A). In the RCP2.6 scenario, changes in the percentage of moderate droughts are relatively small and present great spatial variability. In the RCP8.5 case, however, moderate droughts tend to decrease in frequency over the island, especially in the 2081-2100 period. The latter result is supported by most of the ensemble models (Figure 3.10.3_E4.1_B). Changes in the frequency of severe PV droughts in the considered scenarios are very small. The combination of PV and wind energy is highly positive, as moderate droughts in the control period occur with a frequency almost as low as for PV droughts alone, and the frequency of severe droughts is almost negligible, even below the already very low value for PV energy.

3.1.11 Sicily

Sicily		Wind Energy Prod		PV Prod	
		Land	Sea	Land	Sea
CTRL	1986-2005	1567 (1449 , 1684)	3836 (3712 , 4049)	1566 (1526 , 1627)	1525 (1492 , 1564)
RCP2.6	2046-2065	-11 (-24 , 1)	-43 (-59 , -28)	-6 (-10 , -2)	-20 (-24 , -17)
	2081-2100	-18 (-38 , 3)	-26 (-74 , 23)	-4 (-16 , 8)	-16 (-26 , -9)
RCP8.5	2046-2065	-59 (-113 , 8)	-109 (-175 , -53)	-16 (-24 , -6)	-44 (-55 , -23)
	2081-2100	-143 (-164 , -111)	-264 (-325 , -196)	-21 (-41 , -4)	-77 (-92 , -59)

Table 11.1. Ensemble mean values of annual wind and solar productivity indicators (kWh/kW) in the control period (1986-2005) and ensemble mean changes in future periods (2046-2065, 2081-2100) for the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Ensemble minimum and maximum values are shown in brackets. Spatial averages are computed for land and sea separately. Light (orange) colours indicate the positive (negative) changes in the scenarios relative to the control period. Dark blue and orange colours, respectively, are applied to those cells in which ensemble minimum and maximum values have the same sign. Light blue and orange colours indicate the opposite.

Sicily		Wind		PV		Combined PV and Wind	
		Moderate	Severe	Moderate	Severe	Moderate	Severe
CTRL	1986-2005	52.3 (50.9 , 53.0)	31.2 (30.2 , 31.7)	8.3 (6.7 , 9.4)	1.3 (0.9 , 1.5)	10.8 (10.0 , 11.7)	0.6 (0.5 , 0.7)
RCP2.6	2046-2065	0.44 (-0.11 , 0.99)	0.48 (-0.07 , 1.04)	-0.09 (-0.10 , -0.08)	0.05 (-0.01 , 0.12)	0.02 (-0.16 , 0.20)	0.01 (-0.02 , 0.03)
	2081-2100	0.91 (0.82 , 0.99)	1.20 (1.16 , 1.24)	-0.28 (-0.67 , 0.11)	-0.10 (-0.25 , 0.05)	0.03 (-0.86 , 0.92)	-0.03 (-0.11 , 0.05)
RCP8.5	2046-2065	1.60 (1.02 , 2.54)	1.23 (1.04 , 1.81)	-0.15 (-1.05 , 0.51)	0.06 (-0.30 , 0.32)	0.76 (-0.001 , 1.59)	0.06 (-0.01 , 0.17)
	2081-2100	3.62 (2.83 , 4.56)	2.88 (2.16 , 3.97)	-0.84 (-1.15 , -0.12)	-0.01 (-0.26 , 0.21)	1.60 (0.11 , 3.04)	0.09 (0.02 , 0.24)

Table 11.2. Ensemble mean frequency of moderate and severe productivity drought days (%) in the control time period, as well as the ensemble mean changes in the frequency of drought days (%) in the different time periods considered for the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Ensemble minimum and maximum values are given in brackets. Averages are computed over land. Blue (orange) colours indicate a drought decrease (increase) in the scenarios. The scenario changes are percentages with respect to the total number of days in the respective period, not with respect to the control value. Dark blue and orange colours, respectively, are applied to those cells in which ensemble minimum and maximum values have the same sign. Light blue and orange colours indicate the opposite.

Wind energy productivity:

All the scenarios in both 2046-2065 and 2081-2100 periods show a tendency to decreasing W_{prod} (Figure 3.11.3_E2_A). However, the magnitude of the decreases varies. As occurs in other regions, RCP8.5 in the 2081-2100 period shows the most important decrease, specially over the sea to the north and to the south of Sicily. The southern minimum of Sicily encompasses Malta, where a rather large reduction of 10% with respect to the control value is projected in this scenario and period over land (Table 9.1). The reduction over land in Sicily is smaller in absolute terms, but reaches a value of 9% with respect to the control value which is also clearly lower than in Malta. The uncertainty analysis (Figure 3.11.3_E2_B) shows that the late century reduction in RCP8.5 is robust, with a nearly complete agreement of all models. Previous studies (Tobin et al. 2015, 2016) also show a general decrease, which is more important in Tobin et al. (2015).

Photovoltaic energy productivity:

The spatial pattern of photovoltaic productivity changes is represented in Figure_3.11.3_E1_A (Deliverable 4.3), showing an extended decrease for both scenarios and both periods. The 2081-2100 period for RCP8.5 presents the largest negative changes. Over land, the decreases are lower than 2% of the control productivity in spatial average over Sicily (Table 11.1), while over Malta the decrease reaches 3% in the RCP8.5 scenario at the end of the century (Table 9.1). The decreases are larger over the sea, particularly over the southern part of the domain. Productivity decreases are rather small for RCP2.6.

Energy productivity droughts:

Wind droughts are remarkably more frequent over land than over the sea in the control period (Figure 3.11.3_3.1_A). The east of Sicily seems the most vulnerable area of the domain to be affected by wind droughts. Overall, wind productivity droughts tend to experience an increase in occurrence in both scenarios (Tables 9.2, 11.2). This increase is particularly important in the 2081-2100 period of the RCP8.5 scenario, and higher in Malta than in Sicily. In this case, most of the ensemble models provide an increase in the occurrence of wind droughts and the result is therefore robust (Figure 3.11.3_E3.1_B). Changes in the frequency of wind droughts in these islands are consistent with the observed changes in wind productivity (Figure_3.11.3_E2_A). As to PV droughts, we observe that these are, in the control period, largest in Sicily - specially to the north of the island (Figure 3.11.3_E4.1_A). Projected changes in the frequency of moderate PV droughts are small both in Malta and in Sicily. Severe PV droughts are very infrequent in both islands small, and practically no change is projected in the future. The combination of PV and wind energy is very positive in Sicily both for moderate and severe droughts in the control period, while in Malta a strongly positive effect is found only for severe droughts. In contrast to most other islands, a clear increase is projected in the future for combined moderate droughts in Malta, reaching a value of 7.55% of all days (28 days more per year) in RCP8.5 at the end of the century.

3.1.12 Concluding remarks

In terms of wind productivity two landmark studies should be used to contrast the results of this report for the Mediterranean and Baltic islands in terms of W_{prod} : Tobin et al. (2015) and Tobin et al. (2016). For the Atlantic islands, no studies are available to the author's knowledge. Tobin et al. (2015) aims at assessing future changes in the potential for wind power generation over the whole Europe. For this purpose, model projections from the ENSEMBLES project are used. They show with a high level of confidence that, under the A1B scenario, over most of Europe, changes in wind power potential will remain within ± 15 and ± 20 % by mid and late century respectively. These changes are mainly related to a tendency toward a decrease of the wind power potential over Mediterranean areas and an increase over Northern Europe. On the other hand, Tobin et al. (2016) investigate the impacts of climate change on future European wind power generation potential, using Euro-Cordex regional climate simulations. In this respect, they found that, under two greenhouse gas concentration scenarios, future changes in the annual energy yield of the European wind farms as a whole will remain within $\pm 5\%$ across the 21st century, with the southern regions such as the Iberian and Italian areas being likely the most affected ones. Main results in previous sections show the same results than the above-mentioned studies: a general decrease of wind energy productivity over the Mediterranean region, with a more important decrease for the RCP8.5 scenario. Some regional differences can be also observed for some Mediterranean islands like Crete, Sardinia or Corsica. With respect to the North Atlantic islands, it is interesting that wind productivity increases for the Canary Islands in RCP8.5 scenario, a result that deserves more attention.

Results from photovoltaic energy productivity show also similar results to previous analysis for the Mediterranean area (Jerez et al., 2015) as we have mentioned for each of the regions analysed. In general, small changes are projected for the photovoltaic productivity in every area studied, with slightly more important changes in the Baltic region. There are less studies for the Atlantic archipelagos (Solaun et al., 2019), where the fact that islands are at larger distances from continents makes the study even more appropriated. However, the coarse resolution of the climate simulations and the fact that Azores is very close to the model boundaries, require some caution about the results. More complex patterns are found for these regions and positive changes are projected in some cases.

With respect to the uncertainty in the photovoltaic projections, it is important to consider some recommendations, taking into account some studies related mostly to solar radiation at the surface. Some papers have shown that surface solar radiation over the Euro-Mediterranean area projected by GCM will increase, and as a consequence also the photovoltaic (PV) productivity in the future (Bartok et al., 2017, Wild et al., 2015). However, most of the regional climate models project a decrease in surface solar radiation for the same period over Europe (Jerez et al. 2015) with respect of a historical period, which shows a discrepancy that is under study (Gutiérrez et al. 2020, Boé et al. 2019). Some papers have already shown the importance of the impact of aerosols in regional climate projections (Nabat et al. 2015, Drugé et al. 2019) but most of regional climate models do not include aerosols evolution in their future simulation runs, which makes them not able to include their effects. In the ensemble of regional climate models included in this project, none of the simulations include aerosols evolution. This fact increases uncertainty in photovoltaic energy projections over the islands, that could experience a higher increase in the Mediterranean area and over the Canary Islands due to an increase in surface solar radiation as has been shown

by Nabat et al. 2015 and Drugé et al. 2019 in experiments with CNRM-RCSM4 and ALADIN6.2 models. However, the fact that the models including aerosols evolution project a positive change means that, despite of the uncertainty, the changes would be probably positive, due to the direct effect of aerosols, which would reduce the risk of the worst-case scenario: a decrease in the solar resource.

From the above analysis we can conclude that that, in the regions of study, in the control time period, wind droughts are much more frequent than PV droughts. This is in line with results from the study of Raynaud et al. (2018), in which the authors compute energy productivity droughts in 12 European regions for a 30-year period that extends from 1983 to 2012. This result highlights the steadier nature of the solar productivity in comparison to wind productivity over time. Wind droughts are more frequent in the Mediterranean islands than in Madeira, the Canary Islands or the Baltic Islands. The occurrence of PV droughts is relatively low with the exception of regions such as the Baltic Islands, where they are more prone to develop. To our knowledge, there are no published studies addressing future changes in productivity droughts. Projected changes in the frequency of droughts are small, with changes that generally do not attain a magnitude greater than 5% of the days. The combination of PV and wind energy has generally very positive effects on the frequency of droughts, particularly severe droughts whose frequency is very small (for some islands even below the already low values of severe PV droughts).

3.2 Case studies

In this section we perform a more detailed analysis of the more relevant findings of the previous section for three different areas: (i) the Canary Islands, (ii) Crete and (iii) Cyprus. The reasons for our choice are several. On the one hand, we choose the Canary Islands, in the Atlantic domain, because this region shows results that differ in several aspects from the ones of the other islands, as discussed before. On the other hand, we study in detail Crete and Cyprus because previous studies of wind energy projections do not cover these islands of the Mediterranean region, and despite their relative proximity the future projections for wind energy productivity are very different for both islands. Future changes in PV productivity are generally smaller than changes in wind energy productivity, and the differences among islands are not remarkable; as a consequence, we base our selection mainly on the characteristics of wind energy productivity. Additionally, the selected three regions also present interesting features that make them promising to study productivity droughts. For instance, in the Canary Islands, in the control period the wind drought frequencies are clearly smaller than in other islands and severe PV droughts are almost non-existent, while in RCP8.5 scenario both wind and PV droughts become less frequent, especially at the end of the 21st century. In Crete, a rather high wind energy productivity is associated to much higher wind drought frequencies than in the Canary Islands, and in the future wind and PV droughts are projected to decrease or remain roughly unchanged. In Cyprus, in the RCP8.5 scenario, a marked increase in the frequency of wind droughts occurs, whereas a decrease in the number of moderate PV droughts takes place.

Our analysis focuses on the study of time series which provide insight into the seasonal and interannual evolution of the different indicators. We first comment on the results obtained for the productivity indicators and then analyse energy productivity droughts.

3.2.1 Canary Islands

The annual and seasonal variability analysis for W_{prod} , as observed in Figure 1.1, shows that this region has a weak seasonal cycle. The maximum of W_{prod} occurs in summer but is close to spring values, probably associated with maximum activity in trade winds. The former can be seen in the calculated period 20-years means (not shown here). The minimum occurs in autumn, although it is very close to winter values. However, models project seasonal changes so that the future seasonal cycle should be even weaker. The increase found in RCP8.5, especially by 2081, in the figures from Deliverable 4.3 is mainly related to the winter, also with a slight increase in autumn. In RCP2.6, there are no overall changes. The higher interannual variability is probably because only one model could be used for RCP2.6. A decrease in summer occurs in both periods. Also, the differences between winter, spring and summer decrease by the end of the century in RCP2.6.

Figure 1.1 Annual and seasonal variability of W_{prod} (kWh/kW, in monthly average for each season) for the Canary Islands domain for selected periods for RCP2.6 (upper panel) and RCP8.5 (lower panel). Note that only complete winters (DJF) have been taken into account to construct the time series.

Figure 1.2 Annual and seasonal variability of PV productivity (kWh/kW, in monthly average for each season) for the Canary Islands domain for selected periods for (A) RCP2.6 and (B) RCP8.5. Note that only complete winters (DJF) have been taken into account to construct the time series.

Time series of PV productivity show the expected seasonal pattern with higher values in central months of the year. In general, a substantial relative interannual variability of PV productivity over the Canary Islands is found, except for summer months.

Future negative changes can be appreciated easily for summer in RCP8.5 and RCP2.6, particularly in RCP8.5 at the end of the century. PV productivity tends to decrease also in spring and autumn in RCP8.5. These changes are responsible of the annual mean changes in PV productivity projected over the domain. In other seasons changes are less clear due to the higher interannual variability.

Figure 1.3. Ensemble mean frequency (%) and maximum number of consecutive energy drought days (cedd) for wind (A), photovoltaic (PV; B) and combined PV and wind (C) moderate droughts in the Canary Islands (note that means have been exclusively computed over land). Orange dots (not annotated) are computed for the control time period (1986-2005) taking into account the model available for the RCP2.6 scenario, whilst red dots (not annotated) are calculated for the control time period considering the models available for the RCP8.5 case (see Section 2.4 for details). Annotated orange and red circles are calculated for the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios, respectively, for P1 (2046-2065) and P2 (2081-2100).

In the subsequent analysis we concentrate on the examination of moderate energy droughts. Before we start with the study of the time series, we first focus on Figure 1.3. This expands results presented in Table 4.2 and provides a good overview regarding the ensemble mean frequency (%) and maximum number of consecutive energy drought days (cedd) for the different time periods and scenarios considered. We observe that wind drought episodes are much more frequent and of a longer duration than PV events. Both the frequency and the maximum duration of combined PV and wind energy droughts tend to take intermediate values between both. Wind, PV and combined energy productivity droughts, respectively, experience a decrease in frequency and maximum duration in the RCP8.5 scenario (compare red dots in Figure 1.3). Changes in the frequency and maximum duration of drought episodes in the RCP2.6 scenario are not homogeneous (compare orange dots).

Figure 1.4. Annual and seasonal number of moderate wind drought days for the Canary Islands domain for the selected periods for (A) RCP2.6 and (B) RCP8.5 scenarios. Note that only complete winters (DJF) have been taken into account to construct the time series.

Figure 1.5. Annual and seasonal number of moderate PV drought days for the Canary Islands domain for the selected periods for (A) RCP2.6 and (B) RCP8.5 scenarios. Note that only complete winters (DJF) have been taken into account to construct the time series.

Figure 1.6. Annual and seasonal number of moderate combined PV and wind drought days for the Canary Islands domain for the selected periods for (A) RCP2.6 and (B) RCP8.5 scenarios. Note that only complete winters (DJF) have been taken into account to construct the time series.

Figures 1.4 to 1.6 show time series of the seasonal number of days with wind, PV and combined PV and wind moderate drought conditions, respectively, averaged over the studied domain. Regarding wind productivity droughts, we observe that these are more frequent in winter and autumn and take the minimum values in summer (Figure 1.4). This result is consistent with the seasonal cycle of the wind productivity, with maximum values in spring/summer, when wind trades intensify. In both scenarios interannual variability is larger in the RCP2.6 case, given that this scenario accounts for just one model (see Section 2.4 for details). In the RCP8.5 scenario, a decrease in the number of wind drought days can be observed in winter and autumn in both time periods. The decreased number of wind drought days found in RCP8.5 scenario can be therefore mainly attributed to the wind productivity increase that occurs in winter and autumn.

Focusing on PV droughts we note that, in line with what has been found for the wind productivity, droughts are more frequent in winter in autumn (Figure 1.5). Whilst wind droughts are less prone to occur in spring and summer in both cases, PV droughts are now almost absent in these two seasons. This is consistent with prevailing anticyclonic conditions in spring and summer and higher atmospheric instability associated with the arrival of Atlantic fronts in winter and autumn. Therefore, annual mean changes in the frequency of PV droughts are largely set by insolation changes in the winter season. Interannual variations are largest in winter. In the RCP8.5 scenario, PV droughts experience a remarkable drop in frequency in winter, especially at the end of the 21st century. This is again consistent with the subtle increase of the PV productivity observed in this season. In both RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios PV productivity experiences a decrease in summer in the two considered time periods (Figure 1.2). Interestingly, this is not linked to a noticeable increase in the frequency of PV droughts in summer, which suggests that

the productivity decrease is mostly evenly distributed among most summer days and is not mainly due to larger daily variability in surface solar radiation.

Regarding the seasonal cycle of combined PV and wind droughts (Figure 1.6), we note that this is in all time periods and scenarios qualitatively similar to that found for wind droughts. However, now the frequency of droughts has a smaller magnitude than in the case of wind droughts, as expected from the combination with a low variability energy source like PV. Wind productivity, which has a greater magnitude and a larger variability in time than PV productivity, seems to control the seasonal cycle to a larger extent. In this case, as for wind droughts, a decrease in the frequency of combined droughts occurs in winter and autumn in both periods of the RCP8.5 scenario.

3.2.2 Crete

As can be observed in Figure 2.1, no clear seasonal cycle is obtained for this region, although differences exist between seasons. The maximum in W_{prod} occurs in winter and summer in the control period, but the differences between winter, spring and summer are weakened in the future periods. This is because a decrease of W_{prod} occurs in winter, while a remarkable increase occurs in summer, especially in the 2081-2100 period. This combination of changes could cause even a shift from a winter to a summer yearly maximum of W_{prod} at the end of the century, which is a singular feature of Crete in comparison to other Mediterranean islands. On the other hand, the annual variability seems to be slightly higher in winter. RCP2.6 is generally similar to RCP8.5, but the annual variability is higher, probably because the model ensemble is composed of less models. Another fact worth mentioning is that an important increase occurs in summer in the 2081-2100 period in RCP2.6.

Figure 2.1. Annual and seasonal variability of W_{prod} (kWh/kW, in monthly average for each season) for Crete domain for selected periods for RCP2.6 (upper panel) and RCP8.5 (lower panel). Note that only complete winters (DJF) have been taken into account to construct the time series.

Figure 2.2. Annual and seasonal variability of PV productivity (kWh/kW, in monthly average for each season) for Crete domain for selected periods for (A) RCP2.6 and (B) RCP8.5. Note that only complete winters (DJF) have been taken into account to construct the time series.

The seasonal cycle for Crete region and PV productivity is shown in Figure 2.2. Winter months are more variable than the rest of the seasons. In comparison, Crete region presents less interannual variability than the Canary Islands. Summer months are especially stable, with low interannual variability for the control period or future periods in both scenarios.

A slight decrease in PV productivity is observed for spring and summer months in RCP2.6. The spring and particularly the summer decreases are larger in RCP8.5, and extend into autumn, which does not happen in RCP2.6. Winter months do not show significant changes in PV productivity in any of the projected scenarios.

Comparing Crete with the Canary Islands region, it can be observed that the amplitude of the seasonal cycle for Canary Islands is lower, with more PV productivity in winter months and less PV productivity in summer than for the Crete domain.

Figure 2.3. Ensemble mean frequency (%) and maximum number of consecutive energy drought days (cedd) for wind (A), photovoltaic (PV; B) and combined PV and wind (C) moderate droughts in Crete (note that means have been exclusively computed over land). Orange dots (not annotated) are computed for the control time period (1986-2005) taking into account the models available for the RCP2.6 scenario, whilst red dots (not annotated) are calculated for the control time period considering the models available for the RCP8.5 case (see Section 2.4 for details). Annotated orange and red circles are calculated for the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios, respectively, for P1 (2046-2065) and P2 (2081-2100).

Addressing moderate energy productivity droughts, it is interesting to note that the frequency of moderate wind and PV droughts decreases regardless of the scenario and time period chosen (Figure 2.3). In strong contrast, combined energy droughts will increase in frequency in all cases except for the 2045-2065 time period of the RCP2.6 scenario. These contradictory changes could be due to a lower complementarity between wind and PV in Crete, as the high summer wind productivity coincides with the maximum PV productivity in the year. Changes in the duration of the energy productivity droughts are not greater than 3 days and present a different response depending on the energy source, scenario and time period chosen.

Figure 2.4. Annual and seasonal number of moderate wind drought days for Crete domain for the selected periods for (A) RCP2.6 and (B) RCP8.5 scenarios. Note that only complete winters (DJF) have been taken into account to construct the time series.

Figure 2.5. Annual and seasonal number of moderate PV drought days for Crete domain for the selected periods for (A) RCP2.6 and (B) RCP8.5 scenarios. Note that only complete winters (DJF) have been taken into account to construct the time series.

Figure 2.6. Annual and seasonal number of moderate combined PV and wind drought days for Crete domain for the selected periods for (A) RCP2.6 and (B) RCP8.5 scenarios. Note that only complete winters (DJF) have been taken into account to construct the time series.

Focusing on wind droughts, we note that the seasonal pattern found is different to that observed for the Canary Islands (Figure 2.4). Wind droughts are here more frequent in in spring and autumn and are less prone to occur in winter and summer. This pattern is consistent with the seasonal cycle of wind productivity (Figure 2.1). Interannual variability is relatively large in all seasons, especially in the RCP2.6 scenario. In both scenarios, a future decrease of the number of days in which wind droughts develop is projected in summer, and less clearly in autumn. In the RCP8.5 scenario, winter frequency of droughts experiences a notable increase, especially in the 2081-2100 time period.

Putting the focus on PV droughts, we observe that these present a similar seasonal pattern to that found for the Canary Islands domain (Figure 2.5). This is, as stated above, consistent with more cloudiness in winter and a more stable (anticyclonic) situation in summer. The fact that PV droughts are almost non-existent in spring and summer indicates, once more, that insolation changes in winter and autumn seasons largely determine the annual mean frequency of PV droughts. Therefore, the reduction of the PV productivity observed in both scenarios in summer, does not have an impact on the annual frequency of moderate PV droughts. Interannual variations of PV droughts are again largest in autumn and winter, especially in the RCP2.6 scenario. Winter and autumn productivity changes in the scenarios relative to the control time period (1986-2005) are small and so are changes in the frequency droughts.

Regarding the seasonal cycle of combined PV and wind productivity droughts (Figure 2.6), we observe that this presents important differences with respect to the seasonal cycle of wind droughts. We first note that the frequency of combined droughts is smaller than in the wind case. Whereas the frequency of both wind and combined droughts attains a maximum in autumn, now

the occurrence of droughts in spring and summer becomes smaller. This leads to a similar number of days of combined droughts in all seasons but autumn, when these become remarkably more frequent. The fact that the occurrence of combined droughts decreases in spring and summer to a larger extent than in other seasons may be related to an increase of solar productivity, which is more stable in time than wind productivity. Solar productivity may also cause, for a given season, a reduction in the amplitude of interannual variations relative to that found for wind droughts. As for the wind case, a clear increase in the occurrence of combined droughts is observed in winter in the RCP8.5 scenario, especially in the 2081-2100 period. However, the decrease in the frequency of droughts observed in the RCP8.5 scenario by the end of the century in summer for wind droughts, now is not so evident.

3.2.3 Cyprus

From Figure 3.1, the seasonal variability in W_{prod} shows no important differences between summer and autumn, with a clear maximum occurring in winter. The differences with Crete are really large, both in the seasonal cycle and in the productivity values, which are clearly lower in Cyprus. With respect to the annual variability, it seems to be higher in winter in RCP2.6. Important decreases of W_{prod} occur in future periods for summer, autumn and winter in RCP8.5, with no clear changes in spring. RCP2.6 is associated with no important changes in the mean values of future periods, as opposed to RCP8.5.

Figure 3.1. Annual and seasonal variability of W_{prod} (kWh/kW, in monthly average for each season) for Cyprus domain for selected periods for RCP2.6 (upper panel) and RCP8.5 (lower panel). Note that only complete winters (DJF) have been taken into account to construct the time series.

Figure 3.2. Annual and seasonal variability of PV productivity (kWh/kW, in monthly average for each season) for Cyprus domain for selected periods for (A) RCP2.6 and (B) RCP8.5. Note that only complete winters (DJF) have been taken into account to construct the time series.

In contrast to the large differences in wind energy productivity between both islands, the seasonal pattern of Cyprus domain (Figure 3.2) is similar to the one shown for Crete in terms of its range, and also the future projected changes are similar for the different seasons.

There is a decrease in photovoltaic productivity in spring and summer months of both scenarios, more noticeable in RCP8.5 in summer. On the other hand, there is no clear decrease in winter months, which are the ones with higher interannual variability. RCP2.6 projects a highly variable productivity for these months in both periods. In autumn, a decrease is observed in RCP8.5, whereas it is more difficult to see a clear decrease in RCP2.6.

In general, changes are larger at the end of the century 2081-2100 (orange line) than at mid-century, which happens for the three regions under study.

Figure 3.3. Ensemble mean frequency (%) and maximum number of consecutive energy drought days (cedd) for wind (A), photovoltaic (PV; B) and combined PV and wind (C) moderate droughts in Cyprus (note that means have been exclusively computed over land). Orange dots (not annotated) are computed for the control time period (1986-2005) taking into account the models available for the RCP2.6 scenario, whilst red dots (not annotated) are calculated for the control time period considering the models available for the RCP8.5 case (see Section 2.4 for details). Annotated orange and red circles are calculated for the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios, respectively, for P1 (2046-2065) and P2 (2081-2100).

To start the analysis of moderate energy productivity droughts we first concentrate on Figure 3.3. In this region, wind droughts are more prone to occur than in the Canary Islands or Crete. Also, the maximum duration of wind droughts is greater than in the two previous cases. In the RCP8.5 scenario, wind droughts become more frequent and experience an increase in the maximum duration. However, the opposite result is found for PV droughts. Combined PV and wind droughts have values very near to the low PV droughts values, which points to an important complementarity of both energy sources. Future changes of the combined droughts are small.

Figure 3.4. Annual and seasonal number of moderate wind drought days for Cyprus domain for selected periods for (A) RCP2.6 and (B) RCP8.5 scenarios. Note that only complete winters (DJF) have been taken into account to construct the time series.

Figure 3.5. Annual and seasonal number of moderate PV drought days for Cyprus domain for selected periods for (A) RCP2.6 and (B) RCP8.5 scenarios. Note that only complete winters (DJF) have been taken into account to construct the time series.

Figure 3.6. Annual and seasonal number of moderate combined PV and wind drought days for Cyprus domain for the selected periods for (A) RCP2.6 and (B) RCP8.5 scenarios. Note that only complete winters (DJF) have been taken into account to construct the time series.

Starting from the wind droughts we observe that, in Cyprus, the seasonal cycle is qualitatively different relative to that encountered for Canary Islands and Crete (Figure 3.4). The fact that this is also different to the cycle found in Crete (another Mediterranean island), highlights the great regional variability of winds. In this case, both scenarios provide a minimum (maximum) number of drought days in winter (autumn). In autumn, days under drought conditions are almost twice the number found in winter. The interannual variability is large in both scenarios and in all seasons. In the RCP8.5 scenario, a remarkable increase in the frequency of drought conditions occurs in the 2081-2100 time period. This is particularly clear in winter, summer and autumn.

Putting the focus on PV droughts we note that in Cyprus these are, consistent with what has been found in the Canary Islands and Crete, almost non-existent in spring and summer and more frequent in winter (Figure 3.5). The fact that, qualitatively, the seasonal cycle in the three islands studied in this section presents a similar shape indicates that PV productivity is less influenced by regional factors. The interannual variability is largest in autumn and winter, especially in the latter. In winter, the number of drought days experiences a decrease in both scenarios, but this is particularly pronounced in the 2081-2100 time period of the RCP8.5 scenario. Again, the productivity drop projected for the scenarios in spring and summer, does not have an impact on the annual mean frequency of drought days.

Focusing on the seasonal cycle of combined PV and wind productivity droughts (Figure 3.6), we note that this presents important differences with respect to the seasonal cycle of wind droughts. First, the frequency of combined droughts is smaller than in the wind case. This decrease in the occurrence of droughts is especially remarkable in spring and summer. Whilst in the wind case the minimum was found in winter, now minimum values are found in spring and

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summer. As found for Crete, the fact that the occurrence of combined droughts decreases in spring and summer to a larger extent than in other seasons may be due to an increase of solar productivity, which is more stable in time than wind productivity. As for the wind case, a remarkable increase in the occurrence of combined droughts takes place in the RCP8.5 scenario. This is particularly sharp in the 2081-2100 time period.

4. Summary

Here we present general insights regarding the analysis performed for all islands, as well as more specific findings derived from the more in-depth examination of the selected islands (Canary Islands, Crete and Cyprus). We first present information concerning energy productivity indicators and then we concentrate on findings regarding energy productivity droughts. The most interesting findings can be summarised as follows:

Productivity indicators:

- Wind energy productivity decreases in general over the Mediterranean Sea as a consequence of anthropogenic climate change, consistent with previous studies.
- This decrease is more important for RCP8.5 scenario.
- Crete shows a different trend, with increases over most of the domain at mid-century in both emissions scenarios, and large spatial contrasts at the end of the century for RCP8.5 scenario.
- Climate change over the Baltic Islands affects wind energy productivity in a different way, showing possible increases or little change for RCP8.5, while a decrease is projected for the lower emissions scenario.
- Over the North Atlantic, a particularly interesting result is the increase of wind energy productivity found in the Canary Islands for RCP8.5 scenario.
- The interannual variability of wind energy productivity is rather high, and is somewhat lower in summer than in winter, at least in the three islands analysed in more detail.
- Photovoltaic productivity slightly decreases over the Mediterranean islands, as has been also observed in previous studies, but the relative change of this indicator is rather low in general. The impact of the possible anthropogenic aerosol reduction on surface radiation in the area has not been considered in these projections. This is an uncertainty source that could modify the future change of photovoltaic productivity towards no variation or even small increases.
- Projected changes of PV productivity over the Atlantic islands are generally very small, with a prevailing slight increase over land. Due to the coarse resolution of the models over the Atlantic, in comparison to the land area of the islands, these results should be taken with caution.
- Baltic Islands are the most affected by climate change, with a higher relative decrease in PV productivity, particularly for RCP8.5 scenario. Such a trend has also been projected in previous studies.
- For the three islands analysed in more detail, the annual decrease over the regions is mainly due to the decrease in summer photovoltaic productivity.
- In general, PV productivity changes are smaller over land than over the sea, and the highest decreases are typically projected at sea areas distant from the coast.
- In the Canary Islands domain, wind and PV productivity show the same seasonality, with a maximum during summer months, which indicates a reduced complementarity between both technologies. In Crete, wind has a more stable seasonal cycle with smaller differences among seasons. However, a maximum appears in winter, whereas there is a

minimum in PV productivity during winter months, indicating some complementarity between both sources. In the Cyprus domain both technologies complement each other well: low values of wind productivity coincide with high values of PV productivity during summer, while the opposite occurs in winter.

Energy productivity droughts:

- In the studied regions, in the control time period, wind droughts are generally much more frequent than PV droughts. This highlights the steadier nature of PV productivity over time.
- The annual frequency of PV droughts is largely determined by winter and autumn insolation, given that in spring and summer they are almost non-existent.
- In the control time period, the frequency of PV droughts is similar in all regions, with values around 10% of the days for moderate droughts and very low values of around 1% for severe droughts, with the exception of the Baltic Islands, where both type of PV droughts are clearly more frequent. Lower latitude islands show generally lower PV drought values, with a minimum over Canary Islands, where moderate droughts occur on less than 6% of the days and severe droughts are almost non-existent.
- In the control period, wind droughts are clearly more frequent in the Mediterranean islands (with values around 50% of the days for moderate droughts and 30% of the days for severe droughts) than in the Atlantic Islands.
- Variations in the frequency of productivity droughts in the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios compared to the control time period are small in general, with a maximum magnitude of about 5% of the days. Changes tend to be greater (in magnitude) in the RCP8.5 scenario than in the RCP2.6 case.
- The seasonal cycle of moderate PV droughts is qualitatively the same in the Canary Islands, Crete and Cyprus domains: droughts are maximum in winter and are almost non-existent in spring and summer. This pattern is caused by an increased cloudiness in winter and a prevailing anticyclonic situation in summer.
- The seasonal cycle of moderate wind droughts in the Canary Islands, Crete and Cyprus domains is qualitatively different. The fact that a different seasonal cycle is found in Crete and Cyprus, which are relatively near, underlines the great spatial variability of wind regimes like the Etesian winds in late spring and summer.
- Interestingly, in the Canary Islands, where energy productivity droughts show comparatively low values, a remarkable drop in their frequency in the RCP8.5 scenario is projected.
- In the Baltic Islands, an important increase in the frequency of PV droughts is projected for the RCP8.5 scenario, for which moderate droughts increase about 5%.
- The combination of PV and wind energy is very beneficial in terms of drought frequency for most of the Mediterranean islands, as moderate combined droughts show a frequency that is much nearer to the low PV drought frequency than to the high wind drought frequency. Severe combined droughts are very infrequent in all Mediterranean islands, even below the severe PV drought frequency in several of them. This points to a notable

complementarity of wind and PV energy in many Mediterranean islands.

- In Canary and Madeira islands, the frequency of moderate combined droughts is comparatively high, and nearer to the wind drought frequency. The case of the Baltic Islands is particularly interesting, as the combined drought frequency is not only below the wind drought frequency but also below the PV drought frequency, both for moderate and severe droughts. This points to a high complementarity of PV and wind for the Baltic islands.
- All previous results have been obtained for land points. For most Mediterranean islands, the frequency of severe combined droughts over many sea points near to the coast is nearly zero. This indicates that a potential future deployment of combined offshore wind/PV platforms near the coast would have two important advantages: a clearly higher productivity than over land (as wind productivity increases rapidly over the sea with the distance to the coast) together with a reduced daily variability. This could limit the need for energy storage and backup sources in case of high solar and wind energy shares in the electricity mix.

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Annex

Figures regarding PV productivity and PV productivity droughts and the corresponding uncertainties, not presented in Deliverable 4.3, are here included and described in Section 3.1, where the main findings for the Baltic Islands are addressed.

Figure_3.3.3_E1_A. Panel A: Yearly photovoltaic productivity (kWh/kW) mean for the control time period (1986-2005). Panel B: changes in yearly photovoltaic productivity in the RCP2.6 scenario, mean for the 2046-2065 period with respect to the control. Panel C: as panel B but for the RCP8.5 scenario. Panel D: changes in yearly photovoltaic productivity in the RCP2.6 scenario, mean for the 2081-2100 period with respect to the control. Panel E: as panel D but for the RCP8.5 scenario.

Figure_3.3.3_E1_B. Uncertainty of the ensemble mean (E1_A). Panel A: Number of simulations that project an increase in photovoltaic energy productivity in the RCP2.6 scenario for the 2046-2065 period with respect to the control period. Panel B: as panel A but for the RCP8.5 scenario. Panel C: Number of simulations that project an increase in photovoltaic energy productivity in the RCP2.6 scenario for the 2081-2100 period with respect to the control. Panel D: as panel C but for RCP8.5 scenario.

Figure_3.3.3_E4.1_A. Panels A and B: Percentage (%) of days of photovoltaic (PV) energy droughts in the control time period (1986 – 2005). Panels C – F: Changes in the percentage of drought days in the RCP2.6 scenario for periods 2046 – 2065 and 2081 – 2100 with respect to the control. Panels G – J: As for panels C – F, but calculations are done for the RCP8.5 scenario. Positive values in C – J indicate an increase in the percentage of drought days in the corresponding scenarios. Moderate (mod.) droughts are presented in the left column and severe (sev.) droughts in the right column.

PV % of drought days EuroC

Figure_3.3.3_E4.1_B. Uncertainty of the ensemble means (E4.1_A). Panels A – D: Number of simulations that give an increase in the percentage (%) of photovoltaic (PV) drought days in the RCP2.6 scenario relative to the control simulation (1986 – 2005). Panels E – H: As for panels A – D, but calculations are done for the RCP8.5 scenario. Moderate (mod.) droughts are depicted in the left column and severe (sev.) droughts in the right column.

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